
HIGH PERFORMANCE MULTITHREADING
FOR
SYMMETRIC MULTI PROCESSORS
ON MICROSOFT WINDOWS

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TO MOTHER NATURE,
THE PERFECT SCIENTIST,
THE PERFECT ARTIST.

ABSTRACT

Heavy parallel computation implies heavy scheduling of parallel executing bodies. Too much scheduling overhead will result in performance degradation. Such degradation is evident while scheduling fine-grain parallel tasks. In such cases, schedulers can take much more computation time than the actual task does. This problem drives computer scientists to research and try to minimise the scheduling overhead as much as possible so as to make efficient use of the computational power. The main bottleneck in a multiple processor environment such as a symmetric multiprocessor environment is the scheduler which can gobble up too much computation time. The more computation time is spent on the schedulers, the less useful work is accomplished by parallel tasks hence, it follows, that by reducing the computational time used up by the schedulers, the more computational time is available for actual work which implies a better throughput from the system. The amount of throughput with respect to the number of processors available is termed as speedup. The perfect speedup for an n processor architecture is a speedup of n though this is rarely achieved because of the incurred scheduling overhead. User-level thread scheduling is aimed to achieve an n near speedup by minimising this overhead.

In our thesis we will take advantage of user-level thread scheduling to, efficiently, schedule parallel tasks on shared-memory multiprocessors while also investigating different scheduling queue strategies.

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INTRODUCTION

As computation power is reaching its upper limit for a single processor due to physical hardware limits, symmetric multiprocessors (SMP) are the most probable next desktop computer architecture. Symmetric multiprocessors have the advantage of simple and cheap to implement hence they can offer a cost effective multiprocessor architecture. Theoretically, a dual processor computer would have twice the computational power than a single processor computer. In reality the throughput is rarely doubled because scheduling tasks on different processors has its overhead which degrades the whole throughput. In our thesis we will try to minimise this overhead as much as possible so as to increase the overall throughput by implementing a user-level thread scheduler which will be able of scheduling user-level threads on symmetric multiprocessors while reducing, as much as possible, any kernel activity inside the scheduler.

In our thesis we shall implement a user-level thread scheduler from scratch which would be able of scheduling on symmetric multiprocessors. Apart from implementing the scheduler, we also investigate and implement three different queue strategies, namely a shared run-queue, a per-processor run-queue and a batch run-queue. The project is implemented on a Windows XP platform which will offer an insight on low level systems programming.

1.1 RATIONALE

Although user-level thread schedulers on symmetric multiprocessors have already been successfully implemented on non-Windows platforms, to our knowledge, multiprocessor user-level thread schedulers have not been implemented on a Windows platform. Our main aim is to implement a user-level thread scheduler for symmetric multiprocessors on a Windows platform.

1.2 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The document is divided into seven chapters. In this chapter we have gave a brief introduction to the thesis which should motivate the reader about our project aims. The next chapter shall introduce a detailed background knowledge about our area of research which includes a discussion on the underlying hardware and the multitasking environment concepts. The third chapter gives an account regarding related work that has been accomplished in the are of user-level thread scheduling. In fourth chapter we start our discussion about implementation issues which make up the building blocks of a typical scheduler while the fifth chapter discusses implementation issues which are more related to symmetric multiprocessors. In the sixth chapter we present the results obtained from our implementation which include benchmarks for vital sections of our project. Finally chapter seven presents the conclusion chapter which discusses achievements, drawbacks and future work.

SYMMETRIC MULTIPROCESSING

In this chapter we shall introduce the necessary knowledge which forms the foundation of our thesis. We first discuss multiprocessor architectures followed by a discussion on the underlying hardware which includes the processor and memory. Finally we discuss the importance of scheduling while introducing the concept of processes and threads.

2.1 ARCHITECTURE

The most common and cost effective type of multiple processor architecture is referred to as *symmetric multiprocessors (SMP)*. SMPs, are tightly coupled, shared memory, symmetric multiprocessor machines [4] which, generally, run an identical copy of the operating system on each processor with equal access to shared resources such as main memory. The main advantages behind such an architecture is an increase in system *throughput*¹ and an increase in reliability. There are several multiprocessor topologies, the following are just a few.

- **Single Shared Bus:** The single shared bus topology (Figure 2.1 is one of the most common topologies due to its simplicity which makes it relatively cheap to implement. Nevertheless, such a topology is not scalable because too many processors will decrease the amount of available bandwidth for each processor hence only a handful of processors can be implemented in a single shared bus topology [25]. Hardware circuitry is responsible for preventing data corruption which could arise when two or more processors access the shared bus simultaneously (in the same clock cycle). The circuitry will lock the shared bus so that only one processor can access the bus at any point in time. Such locks can degrade the system throughput when processors are continuously contending for the shared bus giving rise to *bus contention*.

¹work done

Figure 2.1: Single Shared Bus

- Multiple Busses:** Multiple shared busses is an enhancement on the single shared bus system. With multiple shared busses the load is distributed over different busses which relieves bus contention and hence can be scaled much more than a single bus topology. A more expensive type of multiple buss topology is referred to as a *crossbar switch* (figure 2.3). Processor and memory are arranged in grid with fast switches at the connecting lines. If p is the number of processors and m is the number of memory units than at any one point in time the system could execute pxm writes.

Figure 2.2: Fully Connected

- Fully Connected:** In a fully connected system (figure 2.2), memory and processor units are represented as nodes and a full mesh is established

Figure 2.3: Crossbar

between all nodes i.e. every node is connected to all other nodes hence there exists a dedicated connection between any two nodes. This topology is very complex and very expensive

2.2 FLYNN'S TAXONOMY

One of the most popular computer taxonomy is referred to as Flynn's taxonomy [7]. Flynn developed a taxonomy based on the idea of instruction and data streams. An instruction stream is defined as a sequence of instructions performed by a machine. Data stream is a sequence of data accessed by the instructions. The taxonomy divides computer architectures into four main classes.

- **Single Instruction Single Data (SISD)** This is the architecture which represents the Von Newman computer. In this class one instruction stream acts on one data stream.
- **Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD)** A single instruction stream acting on multiple data streams. A typical example is the ILLIAC-IV which has one instruction processing unit and several data processing units.
- **Multiple Instruction Single Data (MISD)** Multiple instruction streams acting on a single data stream. Some researcher consider that a MISD computer has not been created yet [6].

- **Multiple Instruction Multiple Data (MIMD)** Multiple instructions streams acting on multiple data streams. Shared memory multiprocessing architecture is a kind of MIMD taxonomy.

2.3 SHARED MEMORY MODELS

The two main multiprocessor shared memory models are referred to as *uniform memory access (UMA)* and *non-uniform memory access (NUMA)*

- **Uniform Memory Access:** In a uniform memory access, all processors have equal access to memory and I/O devices. Processors usually access memory through a shared bus. This is the model widely used in SMP architectures.
- **Non-Uniform Memory Access:** Unlike UMA, processors in a NUMA model have their own local memory and can access other processors' memory.

Although SMP is generally considered as a UMA model, a NUMA model exists at a lower level transparent to the operating system. Each processor has a small amount of local memory. This local memory makes up a NUMA model.

2.4 SPEEDUP

The main motive behind using a multiple processor architecture is so that we have more *speed* at our disposition and hence hope to get a *speedup* due to the parallel execution of tasks. The speed of a task is the time a task takes to execute. Speedup is the time a task takes to execute on one processor divided by the time it takes to execute on multiple processors.

$$S = \frac{T_1}{T_j}$$

Where:

S is the speedup.

T_1 is the time for task T to execute on 1 processor.

T_j is the time for task T to execute on j processors.

Efficiency is defined as the speedup S divided by the number of processors.

Amdahl's [2] law says that a task is split up into a sequential part which can only be executed on a single processor and a parallel part which can be executed in parallel. Hence according to Amdahl speedup is defined as:

$$S = \frac{s + p}{s + \frac{p}{N}}$$

Where:

S is the speedup.

s is the task's sequential part.

p is the task's parallel part.

N is the number of processors.

This will generate a steep graph where increasing slightly the sequential part will decrease drastically the speedup. One must note that the *speedup* ratio with \mathbf{n} processors is rarely \mathbf{n} [19] this is due to a certain overhead which is incurred in keeping all parts of the system working in synchronisation so that no processor interferes with other processors work.

2.5 PROCESSOR HARDWARE

A processor is the hardware which is responsible for executing instructions. A processor is composed of several units each having its own job to handle. Processor technology differs vastly from one to the another but all processors execute the same basic algorithm over and over again. The algorithm is referred to the *fetch-and-execute cycle*. The fetch-and-execute cycle is a three step cycle where the processor:

- **Fetches** and instruction from memory.
- **Decodes** the instruction.
- **Execute** the instruction.

Each of the above steps is typically executed by a different processor unit. Figure 2.4 shows an Intel NetBurst Micro-Architecture which is an architecture used in modern Intel central processor units.

Figure 2.4: Intel NetBurst Micro-Architecture [8]

2.5.1 FRONT END PIPELINE

Instruction pipeline is a technology used in modern processors to reduce the units' idle time. Pipelining exploits spatial locality as it is assumed that the next instruction in memory is the actual next instruction to be executed. Without pipelining, the fetch and decode units will remain idle while the execution unit is working and vice versa. With pipelining the fetch and decode units will fetch and decode the next instruction while the execution units is executing the current instruction hence once the execution unit is ready from the current instruction it need not wait for the fetch and decode units to accomplish their task since they would have fetched and decoded the next instruction while the execution unit was at work.

Modern processors incorporate additional hardware to aid the fetch and decode step. One such additional hardware is a trace cache which tries to reduce the time to decode instructions fetched from target and bandwidth due to *branches*² in the middle of cache lines. After being fetched and decoded, instructions are built into a sequence of micro-operations known as *traces*. At any one time multiple traces which represent pre-fetched branches are stored in the trace cache. The trace cache is searched for the next instruction following the active branch. If the instruction happens to be the first instruction of a pre-fetched branch then the fetch and decode of instructions from memory is halted and the pre-fetched branch becomes the new source of instructions. In conjunction with trace cache and the translation engine, branch prediction hardware predicts branch targets based on their linear address [8].

2.5.2 OUT-OF-ORDER EXECUTION CORE

This unit is capable of executing micro-operations out of order. This feature is a key factor in enabling parallelism. If one micro-operations is delayed other micro-operations can proceed around it. Several buffers are used by the processor to smooth the flow of micro-operations [8].

2.5.3 RETIREMENT UNIT

Micro-operations that executed out of order need to be reordered before actually making changes to the processor visible registers. Intel implements a retire-

²set of instructions that are not executed in sequence to the main instruction stream

ment unit which is responsible for such a procedure. The retirement unit receives the results of the executed micro-operations from the out-of-order execution core and processes the results so that the architectural state updates according to the original program order. The retirement unit also keeps track of branches and sends update branch target information to the branch target buffers which will purge pre-fetched traces that are no longer needed [8].

2.5.4 EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT

A task is given a set of resources for executing instructions and for storing code, data and state information [8]. These resources make up the execution environment.

- **Address Space:** Any task can address up to 4GBytes of linear memory and 64GBytes of physical memory.
- **Basic Registers:** Eight general purpose registers, six segment registers, EFLAGS register and the program counter (EIP) register make up the basic execution environment for each processor in which tasks can execute general purpose instructions. These instructions perform basic integer arithmetic on byte, word and double-word, handle program flow, operate on bit and byte strings and address memory.
- **x87 FPU Registers:** These registers provide an execution environment for operating on single-precision, double-precision and extended double-precision floating point values.
- **Stack:** To support program stacks, a stack and stack management resources are included in the execution environment.

2.5.5 HYPER-THREADING

Hyper-Threading technology is a technology introduced by Intel which is targeted to increase performance on multi-threaded operating systems. Hyper-Threading enables one processor to execute two or more separate code streams concurrently. A processor that supports hyper-threading (HT) would have two or more logical processors. Each logical processor has its own architectural state along with data registers, segment registers, control registers, debug registers and

most of the *model-specific registers (MSRs)*³. Logical processors also have an advanced programmable interrupt controller (APIC) which provides multiprocessor interrupt manager.

Using hyper-threading is not exactly like using separate processors to achieve a multiprocessor architecture. The main difference between hyper-threading and multiprocessors is that HT share the same processor core which includes the execution engine and the system bus interface. While powered up, each logical processor can be directed independently to execute a thread, interrupted or halted. Two or more threads could be executed simultaneously, with HT, on each physical processor. The core executes the thread instructions concurrently using the out-of-order instruction scheduling to maximise the use of execution units during each clock cycle.

2.6 HARDWARE MEMORY MANAGEMENT

The processor addresses physical memory on its bus. Physical memory is organized in an array of 8-bit bytes where each byte has a unique address referred to as the physical address. The physical address space ranges from 0 to $2^{36}-1$, 64GBytes. Operating systems do not access memory directly but use the processors' memory management facilities. Memory is accessed through one of the three models; flat, segments and real-address mode. We are only concerned with the flat-address mode and hence shall not describe the other modes.

With a flat memory model, memory seems as one contiguous array of bytes. This is referred to as a linear address space. Code, data and stack are all contained in this address space. This space is byte addressable and has a range from 0 to $2^{32} - 1$. The linear address space is mapped into the processor's physical memory either directly or through paging. With direct mapping, each linear address has a one-to-one relationship to physical address. When using paging the linear address space is divided up into pages which are mapped into virtual memory. Paging is transparent to the application programs[8].

³registers that are not guaranteed as part of the Intel architecture and hence may not be available in future processors

2.7 CACHING

Caching is an important concept in the processor fetch and execute cycle. By caching we mean that instructions are copied to a fast memory known as cache memory. This cache memory is much faster than the main memory and hence on fetching from cache, the data is retrieved much faster. Caching is split up into two levels, level one cache is situated on the processor and is the fastest. Level two cache is generally situated on the motherboard between the processor and the main memory and is still much faster than main memory but slower than level one cache. Logically it follows that highly requested instructions will be stored in cache for fast retrieval. This is referred to as *temporal locality*. Cache exploits temporal locality as it assumes that a frequently requested memory location will be requested again in the near future. It also exploits *spatial locality* by assuming that data near the requested location will also be requested in the near future and hence the values, along with the values in memory locations close to it, are also cached. Instructions and data are both cached. Generally a level two cache does not differentiate between instructions and data on the other hand, instructions and data are commonly cached separately in a level one cache. When the processor wants to retrieve data from memory, it first looks at its cache if the data is not present then a *cache miss* is generated and the data is loaded from main memory. On the other hand a *cache hit* occurs when the instruction or data is fetched and retrieved from cache. Caching is only successful because of the principle of locality. If memory had to be accessed in a pure random way then caching would be detrimental as it would cause more overhead due to the continuously changing cache. Another type of cache is used to map between virtual and physical address. This cache aids the translations process and is called the *translation look-aside buffer (TLB)*. A TLB is a sort of hash table with virtual addresses as the key and the corresponding physical address as the value[1].

2.7.1 CACHE COHERENCE

In a multiple processor environment, every processor has its own local cache and hence a consistency problem could arise where 2 processors have a different value, stored in their cache, for a same variable. Hardware coherency ensures that all processor caches are consistent with each other and with main memory. This is achieved in several ways namely *write back protocol*, *write through protocol*, *non-cacheable* and *the snoopy caches*.

Figure 2.5: Cache and Main Memory [17]

- **Write-Through Protocol:** Any writes to local cache will update the whole memory hierarchy⁴. A flag signals other processors that their corresponding cache line has expired.
- **Write-Back Protocol:** Only the current cache is updated allowing memory to become stale [5].
- **Non-Cacheable:** Shared variables between multiple processors are not cached.
- **Snoopy Cache:** When a processor writes to its cache it send a broadcast and invalidates other corresponding processor cache lines. When another processor requests the location, the original processor will broadcast the value and update main memory.

2.8 SCHEDULING

Modern operating systems can execute many programs *concurrently* on a single processor. Concurrency give the impression to the user that multiple programs are running simultaneously. This concept is called *multitasking*. To achieve concurrency, an operating system uses the concept of a task. A task can be regarded as a job that needs to be done. Tasks are queued in memory while they wait for processor resources so as to execute their instructions. Since a processor can

⁴level 1, level 2 and main memory

only execute one task at any point in time, multiple tasks are queued while they wait for their turn. The queue of ready tasks is referred to as the *run-queue*. If a task is running on a processor and suddenly it stops to wait for some input, the processor would sit idle wasting computational time. Multitasking avoids this by running another task within the processor idle window. The program that takes care of all this is known as a scheduler. A scheduler's main job is to *preempt*⁵ running tasks and loading new tasks. A task is said to have a state that changes while executing. State information is very useful when it comes to scheduling. A task can be in one of the following states:

Figure 2.6: Task States [19]

- **New:** The task has been created.
- **Running:** Instruction are being loaded into a processor for execution.
- **Waiting:** The task is waiting for some event such as an I/O completion.
- **Ready:** A task is ready to continue or start executing its instructions.
- **Terminated:** A task has finished its job and terminated.

A scheduler that automatically interrupts tasks so as to run new or to continue tasks is referred to as a *preemptive scheduler*. A typical preemptive scheduler would take decisions under the following circumstances[19]:

⁵interrupt

- Switching from running state to waiting.
- Switching from running state to ready. For example a higher priority task interrupting the current task.
- Switching from waiting state to ready.
- Task terminates.

A common scheduling strategy for symmetric multiprocessor architecture is to run an identical copy of the scheduler on each processor. The focal point of simultaneous running schedulers with equal access to memory, is the run-queue strategy. With a single scheduler, queuing is straight forward because only one scheduler would access the queue at any time. With the introduction of symmetric multiprocessors, multiple schedulers can access a shared resources simultaneously which can incur an excessive overhead due to shared resource contention⁶. The queue strategy has to address two most common SMP scheduling problems which are load balancing and locality. Generally there is a tradeoff between the two, the more load balancing the scheduler offers the less it adheres to the principle of locality. The following are a few queuing strategies typically used in symmetric multiprocessor task scheduling.

SHARED QUEUE

In a shared queuing strategy, all schedulers have equal access to a global shared queue. This type of strategy is the most commonly used. Such a queue needs to be locked or synchronised so that only one scheduler accesses the queue at any point in time. Scheduling fine grained tasks can result in *queue contention* where multiple schedulers are contending for access to the shared queue lock. This contention will incur an excessive overhead which will degrade the system throughput. Such contention is not so evident whilst scheduling coarse grained tasks because queue locks would have a high probability of being free as other processors would be busy executing the lengthy tasks. A shared queue also lacks to address the locality problem because tasks would typically migrate between processors which would invalidate the processors cache and hence further increasing the overhead. On the other hand a shared queue will offer a perfect load balancing over the processors because no task is thighed to a specific processor so whilst

⁶processors contend for a resource but only one is granted access the rest have to wait

a processor is busy executing a coarse grained task, other processors can execute the remaining tasks on the shared queue.

PER-PROCESSOR QUEUE

In a per-processor queue each scheduler has its own private queue. This strategy could be considered as the opposite of a shared queue because it addresses the problem of locality as opposed to a shared queue which addresses the problem of load balancing. With a per-processor queue, queue contention is eliminated because no queue locks are needed. A per-processor queue also benefits from processor cache because tasks do not migrate between processors hence cache invalidations are reduced. The main disadvantage to this type of queuing is that it has no load balancing and processors can suffer from starvation. Starvation occurs when one processor executes all its queued tasks and remains idling while other processors are still busy executing tasks. One way to try to avoid such a situation is to employ *migration*. Instead of idling a scheduler can obtain tasks from other schedulers. The tasks that are transferred to the new scheduler are said to migrate. One way of migrating tasks is referred to as *work stealing* [18] [13]. With a work stealing migration scheme, processor queues are organised as *Last In First Out (LIFO)*. This allows for queuing and dequeuing at one end of the queue whilst tasks on the other end of the queue, referred to as the bottom, would be the last to be executed. The work stealer employs that an idling scheduler will steal tasks from the bottom of other schedulers' queues hence relieving other processors from the over loading whilst efficiently making use of all processor resources. Although this migration reduces the load balancing problem, it can still incur an extra overhead if too many migrations occur because migration is a computation costly procedure.

BATCH QUEUE

A batch queue [25] can be considered as a hybrid between a shared and a per-processor queue. The idea is to exploit the advantages of both a shared queue and a per-processor queue. With batching each scheduler has its own private queue as well as sharing a global queue. Each processor is assigned a batch of tasks which are queued on its private queue. Extra tasks that do fit into the private queues are queued into a shared queue. The shared queue contention is reduced because schedulers do not contend for access to the queue after each

task but after a batch of tasks. The reduced contention makes this strategy suitable for scheduling fine-grained tasks. On the other hand batching exploits locality because a batch of tasks maintain processor affinity for a longer time which reduces cache invalidation.

A task can be of three main types; *Process* , *Kernel-Level Thread* and *User-Level Thread*. Modern operating systems are capable of scheduling processes and kernel-level threads.

2.8.1 PROCESSES

A process is an active entity of a program or part of a program. It is made up of various parts which are:

- **Instructions:** the actual program created by the programmer.
- **Stack:** the stack is a private memory which the process uses while executing.
- **Data Section:** used to store data outside the stack area.
- **Processor Registers:** such as stack pointer, program counter and general purpose registers.

A process is a type of task and hence it has a state. These states are identical to the task states discussed earlier.

PROCESS CONTROL BLOCK (PCB)

For a process to be preempted and continue executing at a later stage, the scheduler needs to store some process related information to main memory. This collection of information is referred to as a *process control block (PCB)*. A PCB is a process record containing information such as process state, process id, registers, memory information, open files, etc. On preemption, the scheduler will save the running process context⁷ in its PCB and will load another one depending on the scheduling algorithm. PCBs are linked to each other to form queues which the scheduler can traverse.

⁷information

Figure 2.7: Processes, Kernel Threads and User-Level Threads

PROCESS CONTEXT SWITCH

A process context switch occurs when the scheduler switches a processor to another process. The main scheduling overhead in a process context switch is three fold:

- Whenever a process is rescheduled a vertical switch, is incurred, which switches from user space to kernel space so that the kernel scheduler could execute. In a vertical switch, the context of the current process is saved and the stack changed to the kernel stack.
- A PCB contains lots of information hence loading and saving PCBs is also an overhead.
- Since processes does not share the address space with other peer processes, memory boundaries need to be checked before loading a new process so as not to corrupt any other process data. This boundary check is also considered as an overhead. The final step is a vertical switch with switches back from kernel to user space.

2.8.2 KERNEL LEVEL THREADS

Kernel threads are also referred to as *lightweight processes (LWP)*. Threads have a set of instructions, a stack space and processor registers. Kernel threads,

Pointer	State
Process Number	
Program Counter	
Registers	
Memory Limits	
List Of Open Files	
Other Information	
.	
⋮	
.	

Figure 2.8: Process Control Block [19]

Figure 2.9: Process Context Switch

like processes, have a state. Multiple threads can execute within the context of a process and hence share the same data section, code and resources. This sharing allows for a faster context switch because less information needs to be maintained. Since kernel threads share the same address space with their peer threads, no memory management related work needs to be done[19]. This reduces drastically the amount of scheduling overhead. Threads have their own private stack and set of register values. Although context switching is much faster than process context switching, the scheduler still needs a vertical switch which can be considered as an overhead. Kernel threads make concurrent programming feasible due to their relatively⁸ low scheduling overhead.

2.8.3 USER LEVEL THREADS

User level threads are somewhat like kernel level threads with the difference that they are scheduled using a user level scheduler instead of the operating system's scheduler. This type of scheduling removes the need of vertical switches and hence reduce drastically the amount of scheduling overhead. User-level threads have become very useful in the area of *fine-grain* parallelism. A fine-grain task is a task which has a small amount of work to be done. In such a case a situation

⁸as compared with processes

Figure 2.10: User-Level Thread Scheduling

could arise where the scheduler takes much more computational time than the actual work done by the thread. With a user-level scheduler we try to reduce scheduling overheads.

Since the kernel does not have any knowledge of user level threads, the operating system can not automatically preempt user-level threads. User-level context switching is the responsibility of the user-level thread scheduler. There are two main types of schedulers.

- **Cooperative Schedulers:** The scheduler is not responsible for preempting threads. Threads are manually yielded by the programmer or else the compiler could add the yielding functions at compile time.
- **Preemptive Scheduler:** In preemptive scheduling the scheduler implements a preemptive algorithm such as the round robin where a timer is used to provide time slices to user level threads. In this case preemption is done automatically by the user level scheduler. The main drawback is that the scheduler needs a vertical switch into kernel mode which incurs an

undesirable overhead.

2.9 RELATED SMP PROBLEMS

Symmetric multiprocessor environment is very prone to problems. Such problems vary from a hardware level to the application level. The following are just a few.

2.9.1 MAIN MEMORY CONTENTION

Memory contention occurs when two or more parallel instructions attempt to modify the same memory location in the same clock cycle which could corrupt the data in the memory location. This could be avoided by locking the bus before modifying a shared memory location. At a higher level memory contention can occur when a shared resource such as a linked list is accessed continuously. This could easily degrade the system throughput as tasks would typically spend a lot of time waiting on locks instead of accomplishing useful work.

2.9.2 CACHE PING PONG

Cache ping pong arises when two or more instructions executing on a different processor access the same memory location in their cache line. This event causes the first processor to invalidate the other processors' cache so as to keep cache coherency. After updating the old cache line by reloading the new value from main memory, the second instruction, on the second processor, will continue by accessing the same cache line which re-invalidates the other processors' cache. This situation can loop forever degrading the system throughput.

2.9.3 PROCESSOR STARVATION

This problem arises when a processor is left idling while there are still tasks to be executed. Schedulers should be able to balance the load evenly over all the processors by *migrating*⁹ or using a different run-queue strategy.

⁹shifting a task from one processor queue to another

2.9.4 DEAD-LOCKS & RACE-CONDITIONS

In a multiprocessor environment common multi-threaded problems such as dead-locks and race conditions become much more evident and a programmer needs to take extra caution while programming on a multiprocessor architecture. Dead-locks could easily arise when shared resources' locks are incorrectly placed, refer to section 2.10. Race conditions occur when shared resources are not protected with a synchronisation construct hence two or more tasks can manipulate a shared resource simultaneously which would lead to an unpredictable result. Such conditions could be avoided by using synchronisation constructs discussed in section 2.10.

2.10 SYNCHRONISATION

In a shared memory multiprocessor architecture the memory is shared amongst processors. At any point in time two or more tasks running on different processors can access the same memory location simultaneously. This could lead to non-deterministic results and is referred to a *race condition*. Another situation that could arise from the non-deterministic behavior of multiple threads running in parallel is known as a *deadlock*. This situation arises when two or more threads acquire a resource then try to acquire each others' resource. Such threads could wait forever. To handle such situations a programmer is equipped with various synchronisation constructs which help in avoiding such problems. The section of a task's code that access a shared resource is often referred to as a *critical section*. Most synchronisation constructs offer methods to protect such critical sections so that only one task accesses the resource at any point in time.

2.10.1 COUNTING SEMAPHORES

A semaphore S is an integer that upon initialisation could only be accessed through two *atomic*¹⁰ instruction which are *wait* and *signal*[19]. Integer S is only modified by one instruction at a time this is accomplished through the use of atomic instructions. Operating systems offer kernel semaphores where the task suspends on a wait instead of *busy waiting*¹¹.

¹⁰an instruction that can not be interrupted while executing

¹¹looping using processor resources while doing no useful work

Algorithm 2.1 Semaphores

```
wait(S): While S == 0 do no-op;
         S = S - 1;

signal(S): S = S + 1;
```

2.10.2 BINARY SEMAPHORES

A binary semaphore is somewhat like a counting semaphore with the different that S can only be 0 or 1. A binary semaphore can be simpler to implement and can offer enough synchronisation for many situations.

2.10.3 MUTEX

A mutex is a variable that would identify whether a task is within a critical section and hence other tasks can not execute their corresponding critical section. The challenge behind a mutex lock type is the way the mutex variable is set so that no other task interrupts while setting a mutex variable and hence having a chance to access the critical section as well. Before entering a critical section a mutex variable is set. With the above two or more tasks can access the critical section because the instructions are not atomic. Converting the above in assembly code we get the following. In the above if a task interrupts while another is still executing instructions between the first and last instruction then both tasks access the critical section. This problem is resolved by using an

Figure 2.11: Deadlock

Algorithm 2.2 Mutex

```
if(mutex != 1)
    mutex = 1
else
    wait
```

Algorithm 2.3 Disassembled Mutex

```
mov eax mutex          //load mutex into register eax
cmp eax 00h            //compare eax to 0
je critical_section   //enter critical section
jmp loop              //wait if the lock is blocked
critical_section:     //label
mov [eax] , 01h       //set mutex to 1 which locks the
                      //critical section
```

implemented complex processor instruction which basically perform the above operation atomically and hence can not be interrupted. A widely used construct of this type is referred to as a spin-lock which busy waits until the mutex is free. Such locks are useful when it comes to fine-grained critical sections i.e. critical section execute in a relatively small amount of time hence it would be useless to suspend (incurs two vertical switches) contending tasks because the amount of time a task should wait before the critical section is free is relatively small. In situations where the critical section is coarse-grained the programmer may opt to suspend (through kernel calls) the tasks while waiting as too much busy waiting will use up processor resources and degrade the system.

2.10.4 MONITOR

A monitor is a high-level synchronisation construct i.e. the compiler is aware of the construct and it is up to the compiler to implement the mutual exclusion. Monitors make it easy on the programmer as it makes synchronisation simpler. A monitor can be considered as a wrapper as it wraps around variables and procedures. A task can call any procedure within the monitor but can not directly access the variables within the monitor. Only one task can be active within a monitor, other tasks will have to wait until the monitor is free before becoming active.

Algorithm 2.4 Monitor

```
monitor sync
  int i;
  procedure one(...)
  {
    .
    .
  }
  procedure two(...)
  {
    .
    .
  }
end monitor;
```

2.10.5 WAIT-FREE

Wait-free synchronisation, has the ability to synchronise shared resources without the use of mutual exclusion or any other form of locks. Such methods can avoid performance problems due to unpredictable delays while tasks are within to enter critical section [23]. The basis of such algorithms is the use of a primitive complex atomic instruction referred to as *compare-and-swap* which is a processor instruction that compares and swaps a single word atomically. With the use of such primitives and the careful ordering of instructions [12], one can implement a shared resource that does not need lock protection such as spin-locks. With wait-free synchronisation, an algorithm could be guaranteed to complete in a finite amount of time because the unpredictable lock-wait-delay is eliminated. Completing in finite time, also, makes the algorithm non-blocking moreover if all instructions are guaranteed to complete the structure is considered to be wait-free. One must note that any data structures that use mutual exclusion are neither non-blocking nor wait-free [6].

RELATED WORK

In this chapter we shall discuss some work that has been accomplished in the area of user-level thread scheduling which includes custom user-level thread scheduling libraries both for uni-processors and multiprocessors, a Microsoft initiative to implement a user-level thread library and finally we discuss work done on queue strategies.

3.1 MESH

MEssaging and ScHeduling (MESH) is a tight integration of a user-level thread scheduler and a zero copy messaging system [14]. The Mesh scheduler is a fast and powerful non-preemptive user-level thread scheduler which is aimed to reduce scheduling overheads by employing techniques to effectively reduce the context switching overhead. This is achieved through:

- **User-Level Scheduling:** Thread context switching is handled at a user-level hence kernel interaction is reduced which implies less overhead.
- **Active Context Switching:** While saving a context, registers that are not being used are not saved which reduces the context switch time.
- **Inline Context Switching:** Instead of using a function call to save the context, inline code is used which reduces the overhead associated with a function call.

Mesh uses a *First In First Out (FIFO)* doubly linked queue strategy. The head of the queue is never dequeued for efficiency reasons. Being doubly linked allows for faster enqueue and dequeue. Only one pointer is held for the queue which points to the head. On queuing, contexts are placed in front of the head and the head pointer is set to point to the new context. This strategy executes threads in a depth-first fashion. MESH also implements 32 levels of priorities each with its own queue. The MESH scheduler is not intended for symmetric multiprocessors.

Further work was done to convert Mesh to a symmetric multiprocessor user-level thread scheduler.

3.2 FIBERS

A fiber is a unit of execution that must be manually scheduled by the application [16]. This makes fibers a kind of user-level threads. Fibers run in the context of the threads that schedule them and are not preemptively scheduled. The latter means that the programmer needs to take care of switching contexts by calling the appropriate fibers library calls. In theory user-level threads can use preemptive scheduling but generally automatic preemption will incur an additional overhead and hence it is not very preferred in a system designed to reduce the overhead. Fibers is a library developed by Microsoft to be used on Windows platforms. Not much is known about the architecture of the Fibers library. This is because Fibers is a commercial product and the source code is not given out to the public. For some particular reason only user-level threads can create new user-level threads hence, to initialise the scheduler a call has to be made to convert the current kernel-level thread into a fibre. Investigating the library function calls we concluded that the scheduler does not implement a run-queue because the yielding function *SwitchToFibre(newFibre)* takes a fiber as a parameter. This parameter is the fibre that the scheduler shall switch after yielding hence there is no use of a queue. Fibers have the facility of a thread local storage (TLS) to store variables and data which are associated with one user-level thread only. This feature is also present in the kernel-level thread library. Fibers scheduler is not intended to work on a multiprocessor system.

Experiments were carried out with the Fibers package and a custom user-level thread scheduler NTLib [24]. In this experiment Fibers, kernel-threads and Nanothreads were compared with each other with respect to thread creation and context switching. The results showed that as expected kernel threads were the slowest in both thread creation and context switching while the nanothreads were the fastest in both the same cases especially in context switching. In the experiment the packages were further customised which included a pre-processor. The programmer is responsible for indicating parts of the program that could be parallelised such as loops, a pre-processor will then decompose the program into sub tasks and execute them in parallel or concurrently.

3.3 UTHREAD

UThread [22] is a simple user-level thread scheduling library. It is written in C++ and is only capable of running on one processor. Unlike other user-level schedulers, UThreads is a preemptive scheduler. This library is object oriented and hence has several different objects which include:

- **UThread:** This object implements the joining functionality and other functionality such as setting thread states.
- **UMutex:** Implements the mutual exclusion semaphore functionality. The object implements two methods lock and unlock which acquires and releases a lock respectively.
- **UCondition:** This object implements synchronisation through two main function wait which suspends execution and wake which resumes execution.
- **Scheduler:** Only one instance of the scheduler can be instantiated which is an indication that the scheduler is not meant for multiple processors. The object implements methods like suspendMeandSwitch which is a yield function, insert which enqueues a thread in the run-queue and next which dequeues the next thread.
- **Queue:** This object implements the run-queue strategy. It is assumed that the queue is just a normal linked list circular queue because the scheduler is not capable of scheduling threads on multiple processors and hence more complex queue with locks are not needed because only one thread at a time would be accessing the queue.

From what it seems this library is not intended for fast multi-threading because it uses a preemptive scheduler which incurs an extra overhead.

3.4 BTHREADS

BThread [20] library is a user-level, uni-processor thread scheduler. The scheduler can either act as a preemptive scheduler by using a round robin algorithm which preempts the current running thread after a time quantum has been exceeded or it can use a *first in first out (FIFO)* queue to act as a non-preemptive scheduler. On terminating, threads are queued into a separate queue which is referred to as the termination queue. This queue is then accessed by another thread

whose job is to free queued threads' resources such as stack and thread descriptor. This library offers a balance between speed and power. Speed is sacrificed by including extra features into the user-level scheduler such as a preemption and more powerful memory management. Synchronisation is also handled through well known constructs such as spin-locks, wait-locks and mutual exclusion.

3.5 SMP-MESH

SMP-MESH is the modification of MESH scheduler into a scheduler which is capable of scheduling user level threads on a symmetric multiprocessor architecture. SMP-MESH allows true concurrent execution of several user level threads [5]. The main difference behind converting a uni-processor user-level thread scheduler to a SMP scheduler is to run an identical copy of the scheduler on different kernel-level threads. These kernel threads are either manually or automatically bound to a specific processor. Since more than one processor can access the same memory locations, locks need to be implemented to synchronise resource acquisition and release. In SMP-MESH, light weight spin-locks are mostly used to lock shared resources. One of the main shared resources is the run-queue. SMP-MESH uses one global run queue in which each kernel thread will have to acquire a lock before queuing and dequeuing a user-level thread context. MESH's run-queue is modified to a single circular linked list where the head is really dequeued. This dequeuing has to take place so as to avoid multiple processors running the same user-level thread. As regards to context switching, SMP-MESH uses inline and active context switching which further reduces a context switch by 222 clock cycles. The final results show that SMP-MESH obtains an excellent speedup while scheduling coarse grained threads. Results also show that scheduling fine-grain user-level threads is not so efficient due to the shared queue contention.

3.6 CILK

Cilk[21] is a language designed for multi-threaded parallel programming. The Cilk language itself is based on ANSI (American National Standards Institute) C and since version 2.0 has supported all of ANSI C. The Cilk language aims to help the programmer in structuring a program so as to best exploit parallelism and locality. The Cilk runtime system includes a scheduler which is responsible for scheduling the computation over several processors by assigning subtasks to separate threads. Cilk implements a processing resource analysis and would not

spawn new threads if not enough processing power is available to execute threads in parallel. Such threads would be converted to normal function calls and executed on the thread that originally tried to spawn the converted threads.

In an experiment Cilk was compared to Java threads and POSIX threads which are both user-level threads. All three libraries were used to execute iterations 1 through 18 of the Fibonacci function. Cilk managed to outperform both Java threads and POSIX threads. Cilk differs from typical user-level thread schedulers due to its pre-processing stage. Cilk compiler generates C code which is then recompiled using the GNU C compiler and linked to the Cilk runtime system which includes the user-level thread scheduler. The Cilk scheduler uses a per-processor run queue. The run-queue acts more like a stack than a queue because it works on a *Last In First Out (LIFO)* as opposed to a *First In First Out (FIFO)* strategy. When a processor executes all its threads on the local queue it becomes a *thief* and *steals* user-level threads from the opposite end of another processor's queue. This technique is a type of migration and is referred to as *work-stealing*. Migration is used to avoid processor starvation hence maintaining a balanced load over all processors.

3.7 FILAMENTS

The Filament package is a library in C designed to work on workstations, symmetric multiprocessors and distributed memory multi-computer. Its main use is to aid parallel scientific applications. Filaments supports all types of grained tasks from fine-grained to course-grained ones. A Filament is a lightweight thread which can be of two kinds, iterative and recursive. Iterative threads are used to split up algorithms such as loops into parallel sub tasks while recursive threads are used to split up recursive routines into their corresponding sub tasks. These threads are executed concurrently using server threads. On a distributed shared memory system, filaments can communicate with each other by reading and writing to shared variables without the need for passing any messages while synchronisation is achieved using barriers and join primitives. The Filament library uses efficient techniques which are not commonly found in other user-level thread schedulers. Such a technique is that a filament thread does not have a stack which implies that context switching is much faster. Filaments are also independent hence thousands can execute on any node in any order. This independence allows run-time flexibility in choosing the next Filament to run and also facilitates load balancing.

3.8 QUEUE STRATEGY ANALYSIS

An investigation was carried out to compare different types of run-queue strategies on both uni-processor and SMP user-level thread scheduling [6]. A run-queue is the focal point of a user-level thread scheduler. Having the right queue strategy plays a vital role in drastically reducing the scheduling overhead. For example in a fine-grained SMP user-level thread scheduler, a shared run-queue would be accessed continuously hence contention forms around the queue and degrades the system throughput. Run-queues can undoubtedly form a bottle neck in an SMP user-level scheduler because a number of processors would be trying to access the queue simultaneously and obviously have to wait to acquire a lock. Kurt implements different run-queue strategies and compares them. Some of the strategies are:

- A shared run queue protected by a single lock. This is the same strategy implemented in SMP-MESH
- A shared run-queue where each individual structure has its own locks.
- A shared run-queue with dual locks. Such a strategy can handle both an enqueue and dequeue simultaneously.
- A shared run-queue using Michael and Scott's non-blocking concurrent queue algorithm.
- A per-processor run queue where each processor is associated a run-queue. This technique, unlike a shared run queue, adheres to the principle of locality and suffers from an imbalanced load over different processors.
- A batch technique where processors are assigned a batch of threads from a global queue. This reduces the contention at the global queue and adheres to the principle of locality.
- A per processor run-queue which uses non-blocking and wait free techniques to migrate threads across processors so as to keep the load balanced.

Context Switch Results for a scheduler using a shared run-queue supports the theory that with the increase of processors the run-queue contention increases and hence a lot of time is spent busy waiting while trying to acquire a lock. Increasing the granularity of user-level threads on a shared run-queue, a greater speedup is achieved. While scheduling relatively coarse-grain user-level threads, an almost perfect speedup is achieved as a result of reduced shared queue contention.

A dual-lock shared run queue shows a better performance in context switching due to the reduction in the run-queue contention as it implements two separate locks, one for enqueue and one for dequeue. The non-blocking scheduler run queue, like the dual lock scheduler run-queue, has the advantage of being able to concurrently execute enqueues and dequeues in the general case. The non-blocking run queue does not seem to perform as well as expected, and is outperformed by both the traditional scheduler and the dual lock scheduler in this benchmark, which is the essential run queue test. Kurt indicates that the problem could be due to complexity of the run-queue structure.

Per-processor run-queues immediately show a great speedup improvement for finer granularity threads. The main drawback in a preprocessor run queue is that if the program is not programmed correctly a load imbalance could occur which will result in not using the full potential of the processors. To minimize this load imbalance a new strategy was proposed by Kevin [25] which is a hybrid between a shared run-queue and a per-processor run queue referred to as batching. The results show a great speedup improvement over a traditional shared run queue strategy. The speedup is especially noted in finer grained user-level threads where the shared run queue suffered due to queue contention. Another per-processor run-queue techniques which was investigated was the the wait-free. This technique showed the same characteristics as its peer per-processor strategies but showed a reduction in speedup at the coarser grained threads. The problem to this situation was a load imbalance which was corrected by reducing the batch size.

INSIDE THE SCHEDULER

In this chapter we shall discuss the implementation of vital building blocks that make up a scheduler. We discuss user-level thread representation inside the scheduler, the context switch mechanism, the user-level memory manager and finally a description of common library functions which are used to integrate the scheduler with a general program.

4.1 THE USER-LEVEL THREAD

The user-level thread scheduler job is to schedule user-level threads. The first step in building the scheduler is finding a way to represent a thread. This representation will form a thread descriptor which will make up part of the scheduler's building blocks. A user-level thread descriptor needs to contain enough information about a thread which could allow a scheduler to yield the thread and continue executing it at a later stage. The main parts that make up a thread are a set of instructions, a stack and a set of registers. Hence thread creation needs to cater for these areas.

4.1.1 THREAD INSTRUCTIONS

First and foremost a thread needs instructions to execute, without instructions a thread is practically nothing. The programmer is responsible for supplying the set of instructions. This procedure is accomplished by converting functions¹, implemented by the programmer, to threads using the corresponding scheduler library calls. On converting a function to a thread, the scheduler's *UThread-Create()* library call will attempt to create a new thread descriptor and saving a pointer, in the descriptor, to the user-function. The pointer stores the virtual memory address of the user-function's first instruction. Loading the address of the first instruction into the program counter (EIP) processor register forces the

¹hereinafter referred to as a user-function

processor to start executing instruction from the loaded location. Once the processor loads the address of the first instruction, the remaining instructions will continue executing in sequence until the thread yield or terminates. Obviously, loading the first instruction of a user-level thread is not enough to start executing a thread, other routines such as setting up the stack space need to take place before executing a thread.

4.1.2 THREAD STACK

The next thing a thread needs is a stack to work on. A thread stack needs to be independent of the creator's stack because the function that created the thread can terminate while the thread is still running. If the thread's stack is within the creator-function's stack, the memory allocated for the stack would be released on the termination of the creator-function, this would also free the thread's stack which could still be executing hence corrupting its local data. The latter leaves us with only one choice that is to use heap memory² The size of the stack is decided by the programmer and is passed through *UThreadCreate()* as a parameter, pointers to the stack base and stack are saved in the user-level thread descriptor as part of the *ImpBuf* variable. The stack size is also saved in the thread descriptor. Before actually loading the pointer to a user-function in the EIP register, the stack registers need to be loaded so as the thread can start using the allocated stack. This procedure is done by writing into *base pointer (EBP)* and *stack pointer (ESP)* registers, the descriptor stack base pointer and the stack pointer respectively.

4.1.3 THREAD PARAMETERS

The programmer can also opt to pass any number parameters to the new thread. The parameters are passed to the *UThreadCreate* scheduler library call which is the function responsible for creating new user-level threads. The parameters are passed in the form a variable argument list. The size of the whole batch of parameters need to be passed in the *UThreadCreate* function. The size is used by the scheduler to effectively pass on the parameters to the new user-level thread. After allocating a chunk of memory for the new thread stack space, any optional parameters passed are copied to the new stack. The optional parameters are stored in sequence hence obtaining the address of the first parameter will give us

²an area of memory, outside the stack, used by a program to dynamically allocate memory.

access to the whole list. The address of the first parameter is obtained using an ANSI C macro, *va_start* we then implemented an assembly loop which reads the variable argument list four bytes at a time and copy the bytes to the new stack. The size of the whole batch of variables is used to terminate the loop.

4.1.4 THREAD REGISTERS

The third and equally important part of a user-level thread is the processor registers that its using. If threads do not yield, this is not much of a problem but in a multitasking environment threads can be interrupted and continue executing at a later stage. In the mean time the processor registers on which the interrupted thread was running can be used by another task and hence corrupted. To enable a user-level thread to continue executing gracefully, its set of registers need to be restored before continue executing. The registers are saved in the thread descriptor as part of *JmpBuf* so as to be restored when the user-level thread continues execution.

4.2 THE CONTEXT SWITCH

During context switching the user-level thread scheduler uses the thread descriptors to save the processor's registers belonging to the executing user-level thread and loads another set of registers associated with another thread. *JmpBuf_SetT* is responsible for saving the registers. This is accomplished by integrating assembly code with C. Due to compiler restrictions, pointer variables could not be directly integrated with assembly instructions and hence some techniques had to be implemented to work around this problem. The first technique is in the way we organised the descriptor structure. The set of variables in which we save our registers form a separate structure *JmpBuf*. A structure of type *JmpBuf* is included in the thread descriptor *UThread*. A *UThread* descriptor is always accessed through a pointer hence *JmpBuf* would be accessed using the *-i* sign which is incompatible with the assembly syntax. For example if we had a descriptor *desc* of type *UThread*,

```
_asm mov desc->JmpBuf_Reg.ebx , EBX
```

would not be valid.

The way we worked around it is that in the *UThread* structure declaration we placed *JmpBuf_Reg* as the first field in the structure. this implies that the address of *UThread desc- \dot{J} JmpBuf_Reg* and *UThread desc* are actually the same because *desc* points to the first field in its structure. All that is left to do is to load the contents of *desc* into a temporarily register such as EAX then access the fields of *JmpBuf_Reg* directly by applying a displacement operator. For example to store the contents of the register EBX to the descriptor *desc- \dot{J} JmpBuf_Reg.ebx*, *ebx* being the second field in *JmpBuf_Reg*, we would

```
_asm mov EAX , desc
_asm mov [EAX + 04h] , EBX
```

We first move the contents of *desc* in the register EAX. Since *desc* and *desc- \dot{J} JmpBuf_Reg* have the same address we displace EAX by 4 bytes so that it points to *JmpBuf_Reg* second field which is *ebx* we then move the contents of EBX register to the location pointed by [EAX + 04h]. Along with the general purpose registers, eight 80bit floating point registers are also saved using the *fsave* and later loaded using the *frstor* complex instructions. Another problem arises when trying to save the program counter register, EIP. The EIP register is not accessible through the MOV assembly instruction at the user-level. In the Intel manuals [9] it was suggested that the EIP could be read by first executing a near CALL, which indirectly pushes the EIP register on stack, then popping the value off the stack and save it in the descriptor. Although this idea works, a CALL instruction incurs an extra overhead and hence was not a preferred solution.

Another way we worked around it is that we specified an assembly label *geteip*, the label would indicate the point at which a thread will continue executing. At compile time the label would be converted to its corresponding memory address hence by saving the contents of the label we would not need to read the EIP register. A mechanism had to be implemented so as to determine whether the label was accessed by *JmpBuf_SetT* or jumped to by *JmpBuf_JmpT*. The mechanism uses the register EAX to store a value indicating which function last accessed the label. Using a register is imperative because when we jump back to *geteip*, the local stack of the function which created the label has by now been freed and hence we can not rely on any function local variables to indicate who accessed the label last. Register EAX was chosen because this register is always used to store the return value of functions which means that the compiler assumes that EAX will be corrupted on a call to a function hence the compiler will try to

void using EAX near function calls. Knowing this, we can use EAX freely in our *JmpBuf_SetT* and *JmpBuf_JmpT* functions.

Loading the registers back to the processor registers is much more straight forward. Registers stored in the user-level thread descriptor are read and copied into their corresponding processor register. Since we can not write directly into the EIP register, we perform a jump instruction to the saved *geteip* label. Before jumping a value of 1 is written into the EAX register so after jumping to *geteip* we would know that in fact the label was jumped to and not just accessed normally. The distinction is imperative because jumping to the *geteip* label indicates that a different user-level thread has just been loaded and hence execution has to be branched accordingly. After a thread terminates execution it returns back to the scheduler to free its resources (not if joined) and schedule another user-level thread. To free the terminated thread's stack, the stack pointers need to be changed to another stack because a stack can not be freed while it is still in use.

4.2.1 INLINE AND ACTIVE CONTEXT SWITCHING

It is imperative that we reduce the context switch as much as possible so as to fully exploit the power of user-level thread scheduling. Two common techniques are widely used to do just that. These techniques are referred to as *inline* and *active* context switching. During a function call stack base and stack pointers are adjusted and any parameters are pushed onto the stack. In inline context switching we eliminate these few extra function call instructions by actually inserting the function code directly into the program code. This is done by using the *#define* directive. This directive is used to substitute an identifier with a token string in the source file [16]. At compile time a hash-defined function's code is pasted inside the actual program code making the code bigger but faster. A function call takes on average 300 clock-cycles hence by using inline context switching we improve a context switch by an average of 300 clock-cycles.

Another technique to further improve context switching time is to use *active* context switching [11]. The basic idea is to only store and load the registers that are being used. This technique relies on the compilation stage which is the stage that has knowledge of what registers are to be used at any point during execution. By observing and disassembling windows C programmes we discovered that if we had a function A which was using the a register, for example EBX, and then it calls another function B which also uses the register EBX then EBX is pushed

Algorithm 4.1 Saving Registers Inline

```
#define JmpBuf_SetT(jmp_buf) {\n    _asm mov EAX , jmp_buf\

---


```

Algorithm 4.2 Loading Registers Inline

```
#define JmpBuf_JmpT(jmp_buf) {\n    _asm mov EAX , jmp_buf\

---


```

onto function B's stack before being corrupted and popping the original value into EBX on returning from the function.

Algorithm 4.3 Register Usage

```
func_A() {
    _asm mov EBX , 0Ah
    func_B();
}
```

```
func_B() {
    _asm mov EBX , 0Bh
}
```

Algorithm 4.4 func_B() Disassembled

```
func_B() {
    push    ebp        //compiler: pushing stack base pointer
    mov     ebp,esp    //compiler: moving base pointer
    push   ebx        //compiler: pushing EBX

    mov     ebx,0Bh   //user-code

    pop     ebx        //compiler: popping EBX
    pop     ebp        //compiler: popping base pointer
    ret                    //compiler: returning to func_A()
}
```

The above observation enables us to use *active* context switching whereby we corrupt the registers by writing 0h into each register instead of saving them to the thread descriptor. By corrupting the registers we force the compiler to only push the registers that were in use before calling a yielding function. Also writing an immediate value to a register is much faster than writing the value of a register to memory because there is less memory access latency in writing an immediate value. The active context switching also reduces the loading time of registers because not all the registers will be loaded only those that were in use. This active context switching could not be used with the stack base pointer

EBP, stack pointer ESP and the floating point FPU registers. Hence, the latter registers are saved and loaded normally.

Algorithm 4.5 Saving Registers Inline and Active

```
#define JmpBuf_SetT(jmp_buf) {\n    _asm mov EAX , jmp_buf\  
    _asm fsave [EAX + 28h] \  
    _asm mov ebx , 0\  
    _asm mov ecx , 0\  
    _asm mov esi , 0\  
    _asm mov edi , 0\  
    _asm mov [EAX + 08h] , ebp\  
    _asm mov [EAX + 04h] , esp\  
    _asm mov edx , geteip\  
    _asm mov [EAX + 00h] , edx\  
    _asm mov EAX , 0h\  
    _asm jmp exitme\  
    _asm geteip:\  
    _asm mov EAX , 1h\  
    _asm exitme:};
```

Algorithm 4.6 Loading Registers Inline and Active

```
#define JmpBuf_JmpT(jmp_buf) {\n    _asm mov EAX , jmp_buf\  
    _asm mov EAX , [EAX]\  
    _asm mov ebp , [EAX + 08h]\  
    _asm mov esp , [EAX + 04h]\  
    _asm frstor [EAX + 28h]\  
    _asm jmp [EAX + 00h]}
```

4.3 USER-LEVEL MEMORY MANAGER

When using *malloc()* to reserve memory for the user-level thread descriptor and stack, vertical switches into the kernel may take place. These vertical switches incur an extra overhead in creating new threads. Since our aim is to schedule threads at the user-level we need to reduce as much as possible the vertical switches into the kernel. One way to reduce the creation time of user level threads is to remove the need to call *malloc()* every time we need to create a new user-level thread. We achieved this by implementing our own user-level memory scheduler. The basic idea is that we use *malloc()* on initialisation to allocate a huge chunk of memory then we implement a manager which manages this chunk of memory at the user-level. The memory manager consists of a double linked list which resides in the chunk of memory and keeps track of the used and free memory space. Every time a new user-level thread is created, the scheduler requests a chunk of memory into which it saves the user-level thread descriptor and the stack. This chunk of memory is then wrapped within a memory manager list node and the node's pointers are set accordingly so as to point to the next free space and to point to the previous allocated chunk.

Figure 4.1 describes the structure of the doubly circular linked list. The figure also shows how the list nodes are stored in the memory chunk along with the stack and thread descriptor. If we had to *malloc()* a separate memory areas for each list node it would render the whole idea of user-level memory managing worthless because we still use a *malloc()* for each user-level thread creation. Due to this fact it was imperative to use the already allocated memory to store the doubly linked list.

4.3.1 INITIALISATION

On initialising the memory list, we first *malloc* a huge chunk of memory using the *malloc()* call. The size of the memory we reserve depends on the memory number of user-level threads and the stack sizes used during the program, generally the size varies between 50MBs and 400MBs. After Allocating the chunk of memory through *malloc()*, we initialise a dummy node. A dummy node is used so that the list will never seem empty and hence adding more nodes is faster because we do not need to check if the list is empty before adding a node. The dummy node's memory area is allocated using *malloc()* this is so that the dummy node does not take up any memory from the chunk and since the dummy node

Figure 4.1: User-Level Memory Manager

is created on initialisation, the extra overhead is acceptable. Both previous and next pointers are set to point to dummy itself. `mchunk_head` which is a pointer pointing to the last node added to the list is set to point to the dummy node. Every page within the allocated memory chunk is access in reverse order using the `memset()` function. By accessing all the pages from the memory on initialisation, we reduce the number of page faults during creation of new user-level threads. Also the pages are accessed in reverse order this is done to exploit the processor cache as the last accessed page on initialisation would be the first page to be accessed while creating the first user-level threads hence it would typically still be cached.

4.3.2 ALLOCATE

Allocation of memory is done through the *user_malloc()* function which takes the size in bytes of memory to allocate and returns the address of the first byte in the allocated chunk. The *user_malloc()* function accesses the *mchunk_head* pointer and checks the *free_size* field of the node. This indicates the available free space remaining, in front of the node, in the chunk. If there is enough space then a new node is placed at the address indicated by *free_base* and the *free_size* field is set to 0. The *used_base* of the new nodes is the address of the *free_base* address offset by the size of the node. The *used_base* address is the the address which will be returned to the scheduler to place the user-level thread descriptor and stack in memory. The new node's *free_base* is set to point to the next free address and the *ptrPrevious* and *ptrNext* pointers are set accordingly. *mchunk_head* now points to the new node. The *used_size* field of a node contains the size of memory used by the stack and thread descriptor. If *mchunk_head* does not have enough space to create a new user-level thread, the whole list is looped to find any available space that has been freed behind the *mchunk_head*.

4.3.3 FREE

Once a user-level thread has finished execution, its allocated memory for stack and descriptor can be freed by calling the the *user_free()* function. The node representing the user-level thread in memory is removed from the list by setting the *ptrPrevious* and *ptrNext* pointers so as to bypass the node. The memory space used by the node, user-level thread and descriptor is now marked as free by adding the size of the freed space to the previous node's *free_size* and setting the previous node's *free_base* to point to the new freed area.

4.4 GENERAL API FUNCTIONS

The general API functions allow the programmer to implement user-level threads. The functions allow the user to create, queue and manually preempt user-level threads. Due to the cooperative nature of scheduler, the programmer is responsible of preempting the user-level threads so as to shift control back to the scheduler.

4.4.1 CREATION

Thread creation is achieved through the *UThreadCreate()* which takes a pointer to a thread descriptor, a variable list of variables and the total size of the variable list in bytes. This function will then create a new user-level thread by allocating memory for the descriptor and stack while returning the address pointing to the new descriptor. If no optional parameters are passed to the user-level thread, the third argument is set to 0 else the third argument is set to the size of the whole argument list in bytes. Optional arguments can be passed after the third argument.

4.4.2 ENQUEUE

Creating a user-level thread is not enough to execute it. The newly created thread needs to be queued in the run-queue so that schedulers can access it and hence execute the user-level thread. This routine is accomplished through the *enqueue()* which takes a pointer to a user-level thread descriptor. Although the *enqueue()* routine differs from one queue strategy implementation to another, the API function only differs slightly in the parameters being passed. In a per-processor and batch strategy, an extra parameter which indicates the scheduler id needs to be passed. The id indicates on which scheduler should the user-level thread be queued.

4.4.3 YIELD

The *yield()* function halts current user-level thread and pass control over to the scheduler which in turn runs another user-level thread. This procedure, unlike most operating systems, is not done automatically by the scheduler because it would incur an extra overhead due to vertical switching so as to access timers and kernel signals. On calling the *yield()* function, the current processor registers are saved using the *ImpBuf_SetT()* inline function. The registers are saved in the user-level thread descriptor and the user-level thread is queued³ in a ready queue so that execution will continue later. A new user-level thread is obtained from the queue and executed by loading the appropriate registers and jumping to the *geteip* label saved in the thread descriptor.

³3 different queuing strategies are used which will be discussed later

4.4.4 JOIN

The *join()* function synchronises execution of user-level threads so that specified threads have to terminate execution before a specified thread continues execution. This function is most important to synchronise user-level threads with the main user-level thread. When a user-level thread A joins on another user-level thread B, B halts execution and saves its registers using *JmpBuf_SetT()* inline function then adds its self to A's *ptrNextJoiner*. Control is then passed to the scheduler. When A terminates executing, the scheduler will check A's joiner list and add any joined threads to the run-queue hence the joined user-level threads can now continue execution.

4.4.5 SEMAPHORES

Synchronising user-level threads is achieved through user-level semaphores. The semaphore functions *UThread_Wait()* and *UThread_Signal()* act on a semaphore variable *S* which resides in the user-level thread descriptor.

U_THREAD_WAIT

The wait function decrements the *S* semaphore variable of the currently running user-level thread. The semaphore is protected by spin-locks so that no two schedulers can have simultaneous access to the semaphore which would lead to a semaphore corruption. The wait function will then yield after releasing the semaphore lock. This causes the scheduler to schedule a new user-level thread while blocking the current thread.

U_THREAD_SIGNAL

The signal function takes a pointer to a thread descriptor and increments the semaphore variable after acquiring the lock. The signal will unblock the user-level thread so when a scheduler gets hold of the unblocked user-level thread it would execute it.

THE SMP LEAP

Adopting the building blocks for scheduling user-level threads so as to schedule user-level threads on symmetric multiprocessors is more a problem of synchronisation and queuing strategies than stacks and registers. In this chapter we shall discuss further implementation issues concerned with symmetric multiprocessors.

5.1 MULTIPLE SCHEDULERS

The basic idea behind scheduling on symmetric multiprocessors is to create multiple kernel-level threads which, ideally, should match the number of processors available and run an identical copy of the scheduler on each kernel-level thread. To effectively manage the kernel-level threads, each kernel-level thread is assigned a descriptor. The descriptor, which is of type *KThread*, is a collection of vital scheduling information. The basic information consists of the current running user-level thread, *UThread Running*, on the particular scheduler, the operating system kernel-thread handle, *uintptr_t handle*, a kernel-level semaphore construct, *HANDLE idle_S*, an id number assigned on initialisation, *int id*, stack base pointer and stack pointer.

5.1.1 INITIALISATION

On initialisation, the *main()* function creates and enqueues a user-level thread with 2MB of stack which points to a *Main()* function. The *Main()* function is the programmer's entry point so the scheduler always starts execution from this specific function. The *main()* function will then proceed to create a specified number of kernel-level threads while also binding them to a specific processor. The binding is done through the *SetThreadAffinityMask()* Windows call. Binding the kernel-level threads to processors will provide smoother execution because we are guaranteed that a specific scheduler will always run on the same processors and hence reduce the kernel overhead of swapping the schedulers between different

processors. The kernel-level threads will then execute some initialisation code which will save the id, passed as a parameter, set up a kernel-level semaphore, save their own thread handler and save the stack pointers in their descriptor before proceeding to start scheduling. The main kernel-level thread will then idle on a kernel semaphore until the scheduler is shutdown.

5.1.2 IDENTITY

A scheduler identification mechanism is needed so that we could distinguish between the different schedulers running. This is important because without such a mechanism we could not have access to the kernel-level thread descriptor while scheduling. One way is to pass the scheduler id as a parameter to all functions but this would force the programmer to pass the parameter to all other user-level threads which would be messy and also increases the thread creation overhead because the parameters need to be copied onto the new user-level thread stack. Another is to use the *GetCurrentThreadId()* which is a kernel call and retrieves the operating system's kernel-level thread id. This also incurs too much overhead because the call enters the kernel.

Our solution is to use a Windows extension to C referred to as *thread-local-storage (TLS)*. With TLS we could declare variables which have a kernel-level thread specific scope. This declaration is done by using the *_declspec(thread)* preceding the kernel specific variable. Not much information is available on how Windows manages to accomplish thread-local-storage hence we tried to take a deeper look into TLS by means of disassembling. Algorithm 5.1 is the disassembled code of assigning 0 to a kernel thread specific 32 bit integer variable.

Algorithm 5.1 Disassembled TLS Code

```
mov    eax,dword ptr [__tls_index (411C2Ch)]
mov    ecx,dword ptr fs:[2Ch]
mov    edx,dword ptr [ecx+eax*4]
mov    dword ptr [edx+4],0
```

What we can conclude is that windows uses the fs processors segment register to assign memory segments to each kernel thread. After moving *_tls_index*, EAX always seems to remain 0. The value of ECX changes from one thread to another so when the operating system context switches between kernel threads it also

changes the hidden value of the fs segment register. The combination of the offset and the segment register will typically point to the base address of the kernel thread private memory data. This mechanism is used to store the kernel-level thread id which is assigned to each kernel thread on initialisation. Once we have a means to retrieve the id, we can use the id as an array index where each element in the array is a pointer to a kernel thread descriptor.

5.1.3 IDLING

Whenever schedulers try to obtain a user-level thread from the run-queue, which could be either shared or local, and the queue is found empty, the scheduler must wait for any new user-level threads to run. A scheduler could either busy wait or sleep while waiting for any user-level threads to execute. Busy waiting will use up processor resources and since the scheduler can run in a multitasking environment, it could degrade the system throughput. The preferred option is to suspend the scheduler, through kernel calls, while waiting for new user-level threads.

SLEEP

Suspension of schedulers only occurs on a NULL return from the dequeuing *fdequeue()* routine which signifies that no more user-level threads are available in the queue¹ at the point in time. Before actually suspending the scheduler, a flag bit inside the scheduler descriptor is set which indicates that the scheduler is sleeping. The bit is set using the processor complex instruction *bit_test_and_set (bts)* which would avoid any inconsistencies if another scheduler is checking for sleeping schedulers. The operating stack is also switched to the scheduler's proper stack which is defined in the scheduler's descriptor. The stack space switch would prevent two schedulers working on the same stack space which could lead to data corruption (see figure 5.2). The last step in suspending a scheduler is actually putting it to sleep. The latter procedure is done using kernel-level semaphores using *WaitForSingleObject()*. Every scheduler has, associated with it, a semaphore construct which is saved in the scheduler descriptor. This semaphore *idle_S* is used for suspending the scheduler. Using a semaphore construct will actually avoid a common problem which is referred to as the *lost-wake-up* problem. The *lost-wake-up* problem could arise while using a different suspension mechanism such as

¹queue could be one of the 3 different queuing strategies implemented

signals. With signals, a scheduler could be signaled to sleep while simultaneously it could be signaled to wake up. If the wake up signal is processed before the suspend signal then the scheduler will eventually sleep with the possibility of never waking up because the wake up signal has been received moments before actually sleeping (figure 5.1). With semaphores such a problem could not arise because if the semaphore is signaled before the scheduler waits on the semaphore, the wait procedure just decrements the semaphore and hence setting back to 0 which will cause the scheduler to continue execution instead of blocking indefinitely.

Figure 5.1: Lost Wake Up Problem

WAKE-UP

Waking up schedulers is the routine that wakes up idling threads when new user-level threads are available for execution. The queue *enqueue()* function is responsible for the wake-up routine. The routine is fired when a scheduler calls the *enqueue()* function and the queue is found empty. Depending on the queue strategy implemented the routine will try to wake up a scheduler by accessing its descriptor and signaling the semaphore *idle_S* using *ReleaseSemaphore()* and resetting the scheduler's idling bit.

As a matter of optimisation [5], the user-level thread that was destined to be queued is now routed to the *Running* scheduler variable. This direct thread injection reduces the extra routine of queuing the user-level thread, releasing the queue lock, if any, re-acquiring the queue lock by the woken-up scheduler, dequeuing the user-level thread and releasing the queue lock again. In the mean time the queue could be emptied again by other schedulers hence forcing the woken-up thread to sleep again without performing any useful work.

Another optimisation is that while yielding, the scheduler does not attempt to wake up any sleeping schedulers as it would incur an extra useless overhead. In the case that the queue is found empty, the current scheduler will simply continue to execute the yielded user-level thread without queuing and dequeuing operations. This optimisation is achieved by the use of a separate queuing function *enqueue_dequeue()* used solely by the yielding mechanism.

5.1.4 SCHEDULER STACK

Changing the stack space every time we enter the scheduler would be an extra overhead, we could avoid the overhead by using the same stack used by the user-level thread that entered the scheduler. The stack is changed when a new user-level thread context is loaded using *JumpBuf_JmpT*. A problem could arise, especially when using a shared run-queue strategy, that a user-level thread stack space could be accessed by two or more threads simultaneously which could lead to data corruption. Such a problem could be avoided by extending the queue lock so that it is released after a context switch as opposed to release the lock exactly after a dequeue routine. Obviously, in a per-processor strategy this is not the case because a user-level thread will only execute on one scheduler. To prevent

stack corruption, the operating stack space is changed before a scheduler idling as discussed in section 5.1.3 and after user-level thread termination.

Figure 5.2: Possible Stack Corruption

5.1.5 JOINING PROBLEM

As discussed in 4.4.4, a thread join is a routine which synchronises two or more threads so that a specified thread suspends its execution until other thread terminate. The mechanism to accomplish this on a symmetric multiprocessor environment poses some challenging problems. Whilst joining upon a user-level thread within a symmetric multiprocessor environment, the user-level thread which will be joined upon could be in different states [5].

- **Queued:** the user-level thread is still queued in the run-queue and hence is not executing.
- **Executing:** the user-level thread has began execution on a different processor.
- **Terminating:** the user-level thread has finished executing and is currently terminating.
- **Terminated:** the user-level thread has terminated completely its executing and also terminated the termination sequence.

If we have two threads A and B, A is joined on B so that B has to terminate execution before A continues its own execution. Typically what would happen is that A calls a *join()* function on B, the join function will save the context of A in the joiner list of B and continues by scheduling a new user-level thread. When B terminates execution, its joiner list is checked and any user-level threads are queued back into the run-queue hence allowing thread A to only continue execution after B's termination.

In a multiprocessor environment, once B is queued up in the run-queue any other scheduler can start executing B and B can terminate even before the *join()* function is called by A. Upon calling the *join()* function by A, B needs to be checked so as to verify in which state it is.

Figure 5.3: Joining Problem

- **Queued:** if B is still queued in the run-queue then A's context should be saved and added to B's joiner list. The scheduler is then called to schedule another user-level thread.
- **Executing:** if B is still executing then A's context should be saved and added to B's joiner list. On B's termination A will be queued again and

hence can continue execution.

- **Terminated:** if B has already terminated then no routine has to be executed and user-level thread A continues execution.
- **Terminating:** if B is in the process of terminating, care must be taken so that not to add A to B's joiner list after the scheduler, terminating B, has already checked B's joiner list. In such a case user-level thread A would be lost forever. This problem is avoided by using spin-locks which are used to synchronise B's joiner list so that only one scheduler will access the joiner list at any point in time.

The bit, on which the spin-lock works to synchronise the termination of B so that only one scheduler accesses B's joiner list at any point in time is a bit which is not shared by user-level threads but every user-level thread has its own bit which is accessed through the user-level thread descriptor *thr_aux*. It is imperative to use a separate spin-lock for every thread as it is not feasible to lock the termination set of instructions so that only one scheduler can access the termination instructions at any point. Our aim is to lock a specific user-level thread's joiner list while one scheduler is terminating the user-level thread and another is joining on the same thread.

The joiner function needs to access the joiner list lock bit which is accessed through the specified user-level thread descriptor. If B has terminated and its allocated memory is freed then when the joiner function is called on B we could not guarantee an access to the user-level thread's descriptor as the allocated memory could be allocated to a different user-level thread so a NULL check on the memory allocated to B's user-level thread descriptor will not distinguish between different states of B. A solution is to use the memory address of the pointer to the descriptor which is allocated from the stack of the user-level thread that creates the new user-level thread. In such a case the address of the pointer is passed as a parameter in most library calls such as *UThreadCreate()*. Once the user-level thread is terminated, its corresponding pointer is set to NULL and its allocated memory is freed. While joining upon a user-level thread, the address of the pointer is passed as a parameter to the joiner function hence a NULL check could be performed which would indicate if the thread has been terminated or not. The problem with such a solution is that the programmer might reuse the pointer variable to create a new user-level thread in which case the pointer will

point to a different user-level thread descriptor and not NULL which would not be acceptable.

Our solution, although still crude, requires the programmer to specify that the newly created thread will be joined upon. This is done by setting a specific bit in the user-level thread's descriptor. Reverting to the previous scenario, on terminating B, the scheduler will check if the specific bit is set in which case the memory allocated to the user-level thread is not freed hence leaving the descriptor intact. Once the joiner routine access the descriptor, it will either add A to B's joiner list or else, if B has already been executed, free the allocated memory to B and continue executing A.

5.1.6 SYNCHRONISATION

Multiple schedulers running in parallel can frequently compete for resources and hence need to be synchronised. The main two types of constructs used to synchronise schedulers are user-level spin-locks and semaphores.

SEMAPHORES

Kernel semaphores are used to synchronise kernel threads in three main scheduling areas which are, initialisation, idling and termination. Kernel semaphores are implemented through *WaitForSingleObject()* which synonymous with the *wait()* theoretical semaphore function and *ReleaseSemaphore()* which is synonymous with the *signal()* semaphore function.

CRITICAL SECTION

Windows also offers functionality to protect critical section. The protection is done through the *EnterCriticalSection()* function which acquires a lock to enter a section of code. This guarantees that only one thread executes a specified piece of code at any point in time. A critical section is released by using the *LeaveCriticalSection()*. This function releases the critical section so that it could be accessed by other kernel threads. Windows critical section is some what of a light weight synchronous construct. A vertical switch when the critical section is locked and hence the operating system needs to suspend the contending kernel thread until the lock is released. This could be avoided by setting a spin count for a specified lock which would force the kernel thread to spin for a specified amount

of times before performing a vertical switch into the kernel to suspend itself. Busy waiting could increase the performance of locks especially when critical section execution time is relatively small.

SPIN-LOCK

Our preferred critical section lock type is referred to as a spin lock which is implemented at the user level hence avoiding vertical switching overhead. A spin-lock, basically uses a mutex variable to identify whether a lock is free or not. If the lock is not free, the thread will loop until the lock is free. This looping also referred to as busy waiting is where spin-lock gets its name because the thread is spinning around the same few instructions until the lock is freed. A spin-lock is only possible due to a processor complex atomic instruction which is referred to as *test-and-set*. The *test-and-set* instruction checks a specified bit and if the bit is one it sets the carry flag. The checking and setting is all done atomically which means that no other thread can interrupt the instruction while executing. Without such an atomic instruction a spin-lock would look like algorithm 5.2. The

Algorithm 5.2 Spin-Lock non-atomic

```
loop:
mov  eax , lock
mov  cmp  eax , 0
je   cont
jmp  loop
cont:
mov  [eax] , 1
```

spin-lock in algorithm 5.2 will not efficiently lock a critical section because in a multiprocessor environment two or more processors can simultaneously execute the first instruction which could lead to more than one thread loading 0 into the EAX register hence more than one kernel-level thread may enter the critical section at the same point in time. Locking the bus so that one processor accesses the bus while executing the first instruction does not solve the problem, either, because one processor can successfully execute the first instruction and continues executing the following instructions while another processor executes the first instruction before the first processor actually sets lock to one (last instruction), this would also lead to more than one kernel thread entering the critical section.

The problem is solved by the introduction of an atomic primitive instruction, *test-and-set*, which basically combines the first and last (`mov [eax], 1`) instructions into one atomic instruction.

Algorithm 5.3 Spin-Lock Atomic

```
loop:
lock bts lock\_bits , 0
jnc cont
jmp loop
cont:
```

bts which is the test-and-set command, first tests bit 0 from the set of bits defined by `lock_bits`. If the bit is set to 1 then the instruction will set the carry flag register to one. By comparing the carry flag we can identify if a lock is free or not and hence act accordingly. Although the *bts* command is atomic, in a symmetric multiprocessor environment, two or more processors can still execute the *bts* instruction simultaneously hence leading to lock corruption. This problem is avoided by locking the bus while executing the *bts* command. By locking the bus we ensure that only one processor accesses the memory bus while executing *bts*.

The spin-lock in algorithm 6.2 works fine but has one major drawback in a symmetric multiprocessor environment. Kernel threads that are waiting to enter a lock are spinning around a write command which tends to invalidate peer processors' cache this will lead caches to be updated on every spin which will degrade the system throughput. This problem, also known as *the thundering herd problem* can be solved by performing a spin on a read command instead of a write. A kernel thread will try to set the lock bit to 1 if it is not successful, the thread will spin until the lock has a value of 0 than it will try again to set the lock to 1 hence spinning occurs on a read and does not invalidate any caches (algorithm 5.4). Releasing the lock is straight forward, the lock bit is just reset using the *btr* command (algorithm 5.5). The spin-lock construct is used throughout the scheduler to lock shared resources. Spin-locks are used:

- To lock access to the shared run-queues in shared and batch run-queues strategies.
- To lock access to the memory manager.

- To synchronise user-level semaphore constructs.
- To synchronise user-level thread termination sequence.

Algorithm 5.4 Spin On Read

```
loop:
lock bts lock_bits , 0
jnc cont
spin:
btl lock_bits , 0
jc spin
jmp loop
cont:
```

Algorithm 5.5 Lock Release

```
lock btr lock\_bits , 0
```

5.1.7 TERMINATION

After execution of all available user-level threads, the multiple schedulers will terminate execution. Termination criteria is based upon a global variable which indicates the number of running schedulers i.e. not idling. Before idling each scheduler checks the variable *no_of_running* to check whether the current scheduler is the last to idle in which case the termination sequence should take place. The last scheduler wakes up all other idling schedulers, on waking up, schedulers check the variable and if the variable is set to 0 the scheduler exits. The main kernel thread is woken up by the first thread to exit which frees the allocated memory for the memory manager.

5.2 RUN-QUEUE STRATEGIES

In a multitasking environment, processors' resources need to be shared between threads because not enough processor resources would be available to satisfy all threads simultaneously. Threads that are not currently executing should be queued while waiting for processor resources. In a symmetric multiprocessor environment, the run-queue² strategy plays a vital role in controlling the excessive overhead while maintaining a balanced load over all processors. In a single processor environment, the queue strategy does not play as much importance because we do not need to deal with the multiple processor common problems such as load balance and cache locality. Queue strategies try to address the load balancing and locality problems. Generally increasing the efficiency in one will decrease the other so if we increase the load balancing power we will tend to decrease the adherence to the principle of locality. To further investigate the effect of using different queue strategies, we implement three different queue types with the aim of reducing common symmetric multiprocessing scheduling bottlenecks.

5.2.1 SHARED QUEUE

The most common type of user-level thread queuing strategy is a shared queue type (figure 5.4). In a shared queue all schedulers have equal access to a global queue from where user-level threads are retrieved for execution while also queuing up new threads. In itself a shared queue strategy can take different forms varying from a single linked list with one head pointer to a doubly linked circular list with two pointers one pointing to the head and another to the tail. We decided to implement one of the most common types of queues which is a single circular linked list with direct access to the head node and tail node. Adding extra complexity may make a queue more powerful but on the other hand increases the queuing and dequeuing overhead. Since the access pointers which point to the head and tail nodes are accessed globally by all schedulers, locks need to be used to synchronise access to such resources so that only one scheduler is able to modify the pointers at any given time.

Another type of locking is a dual lock type [15] queue access which uses two different locks for queuing and dequeuing this allows a scheduler to enqueue while another scheduler is dequeuing simultaneously. The use of an atomic

²hereinafter referred to as the queue

compare_and_swap [25] complex instruction enables even for non blocking queue strategies where no locks are needed because the sequence of instructions ensures that only one thread manipulates the queue access pointers at any time. In our implementation we used one spin-lock which protects both access pointers (head and tail) hence queue and dequeue routines can not execute simultaneously.

Figure 5.4: Shared Run-Queue

ENQUEUE

The various queuing functions all perform the same basic routine i.e. add the new item (user-level thread descriptor) to the tail of the queue and then point the tail pointer to the new added item. Queuing always assumes that the queue is not empty this reduces several checks before adding an item. On initialisation, a dummy item is added to the queue hence the queue will always have at least one item. The head pointer always points to the dummy item and hence is never null. The two main queuing functions can be distinguished by their functionality, *enqueue()* is the queuing function used to add newly created user-level threads, whilst *enqueue_dequeue()* is a function used by *yield()* to enqueue and dequeue consecutively. Apart from performing the basic queuing routine, *enqueue()*, is also responsible for waking up any idling schedulers (section ??). The shared queue waking up mechanism loops through the scheduler descriptors when the shared queue is found empty and attempts to wake up the first found idling scheduler. The rest of the procedure is as discussed in section 5.1.3.

DEQUEUE

The dequeuing function, *fdequeue()*, dequeues the user-level thread pointed by *head->ptrNext* the head pointers are then set to point to the next item in the queue. Before dequeuing, the scheduler needs to acquire the queue lock through the use of a spin-lock construct. Since queued threads can be suspended on a user-level semaphore, the dequeuing function needs to skip any user-level threads that are blocked. Such threads can be dequeued at a later stage because the queue is circularly linked.

YIELD

The *enqueue_dequeue()* function is used on yielding. This function enqueues an item and dequeues another item while still in possession of the same lock. The use of this function removes the extra routine of first queuing a user-level thread then calling the *schedule()* function to dequeue another thread and continue execution. The dequeued user-level thread will continue execution from within the *yield()* function. If the queue is found empty the user-level thread which is about to be added to the queue is returned immediately hence avoiding an extra enqueue-dequeue routine.

5.2.2 PER-PROCESSOR QUEUE

The second type of queue strategy is a per-processor queue (figure 6.6). In a per-processor queue, instead of sharing a single global queue, each scheduler is assigned a local queue hence there is no need to acquire locks to access the queue. The elimination of queue contention is traded with load imbalance problem because with a per-processor queue, load balance is much more difficult to achieve. Load balancing on a per-processor queue is generally achieved through a migration routine where user-level threads are migrated from one queue to another. In our implementation we do not cater for load balancing within the scheduler. The programmer is responsible for balancing the load over the multiple schedulers. Each scheduler maintains a single linked list with one access pointer pointing to head.

Figure 5.5: Per-Processor Run-Queue

ENQUEUE

Enqueue in a per-processor strategy is much more simple. Since we only have one access pointer which points to the head, any queuing and dequeuing has to occur around the head. On initialisation, each scheduler creates a dummy node and points the head access pointer to it. The use of the dummy node is to facilitate the enqueue routine because there is no need to check if the access pointer is pointing to NULL for every enqueue routine. The queue acts more like a stack than a queue because the first item to be queued is the last to be dequeued (FILO). The *enqueue()* function is also responsible for waking up idling schedulers. The way schedulers are woken up is somewhat different than a shared queue mechanism. Since the user specifies on which scheduler the user-level thread should be queued, we are only concerned in waking up that specified scheduler in the case that it is idling. Also, it is much more difficult and computational expensive to determine if other schedulers are idling and it may not be the scope of a per-processor strategy to wake up other schedulers.

DEQUEUE

Dequeuing in a per-processor queuing strategy is a straight forward routine. The item pointed by `head->ptrNext`, which is saved in the scheduler descriptor, is dequeued by setting the appropriate pointers to bypass it. Once the queue is found empty, the scheduler proceeds to idle by setting the idling bit and eventually suspend.

YIELD

While yielding, the scheduler will only interact with its own local queue. The scheduler will first check if the local queue is empty in which case it continues executing the yielded user-level thread. In the case that the local queue is not empty, the next user-level thread is dequeued and the yielded thread is added to the queue. Like other schedulers the `yield()` does not call the `schedule()` instead it jumps directly to the newly obtained thread from the queue.

5.2.3 VARIABLE BATCHING

Using both the advantages of the a shared queue and a per-processors queue will lead to a new hybrid queue strategy referred to as batching [?]. In our implementation we introduce a variant of batching which we shall call variable batching. Batching is aimed to exploit cache affinity while also trying to maintain an adequate load balance over all schedulers. In batching, each scheduler schedules batches of user-level threads instead of scheduling single user-level threads like in a shared queue strategy (figure 5.6). Once a scheduler acquires a batch of user-level threads from a shared queue of batches, the scheduler will act as a per-processor queue scheduler hence exploiting per-processor strategy advantages, better cache affinity and contention. Using a shared queue also exploits load balancing. Shared queue contention is reduced because the shared queue is accessed much more infrequent hence schedulers will spend less time spinning on locks to acquire shared queue locks. In static batching all schedulers are assigned a fixed batch size. The fixed batch size may not cater for all situations for example if the batch size is too big then the schedulers can starve due to a load imbalance on the other hand if the batches are too small an increase shared queue contention can incur an excessive overhead.

Variable batching aims to address the static batching problems. In variable batching the programmer is responsible for setting the different scheduler batch sizes. This allows the programmer to batch fine grained and coarse grained user-level threads in separate batches while setting different batch sizes for each scheduler. A scheduler which schedules fine grained threads would typically have a big batch size because its user-level threads would execute in no time and hence reduce shared queue contention. On the other hand a scheduler with coarse grained threads would typically have a small batch size so that user-level threads do not remain trapped inside the scheduler batch while waiting for other user-level threads to execute. With a small batch size, extra threads would be queued in a shared queue hence other schedulers could execute the extra threads. The programmer can also control the context switch threshold which when exceeded would switch the batch with another batch. Although, the programmer is responsible for setting the scheduler batch sizes, batch sizes may still vary on execution because batches are continuously resized so as to best exploit load balancing.

ENQUEUE

Thread insertion is somewhat a complex routine when compared with previous insertions. The first step in queuing is to check whether the scheduler on which we shall insert the thread is sleeping, if so the scheduler is woken up while writing the user-level thread in the *Running* field of the scheduler descriptor. If the scheduler is not idling, the queuing mechanism will try to insert the thread in the local scheduler queue. This will fail if the queue is already full in which case the user-level thread is inserted in the shared queue. Before inserting a user-level thread in the shared queue, a lock has to be acquired so as to synchronise shared resource access. The lock used is a spin-lock construct. If the shared queue is found empty, an attempt is made to wake up the first sleeping scheduler. This mechanism is executed in the same way as in a shared queue strategy mechanism. Scheduler descriptors are looped until the first idling scheduler is found in which case the user-level thread is written into the *Running* field and the scheduler kernel semaphore is signaled which will wake up the scheduler.

DEQUEUE

Thread removal is also a complex routine when compared to other queue strategies routines. The dequeuing mechanism first attempts to dequeue a user-level

Figure 5.6: Batch Run-Queue

thread from the scheduler local batch queue. If the scheduler local queue is empty, a batch of user-level threads are obtained from the shared queue. The batch size obtained is variable. If a scheduler has a batch size to accommodate fine grained threads i.e. it would typically have a big batch size and the shared queue is filled with coarse-grain user-level threads then the scheduler would typically obtain a big batch of coarse grain threads which would have a negative impact on the load balancing because the obtained coarse grained threads are bound to take a long time to execute and since they are locked in the scheduler's batch the load can not be balanced over other schedulers.

Due to this problem the batch size is resized while obtaining a batch from the shared queue so that if coarse grained user-level threads are queued and the batch size is too large, the batch maximum size is reduced. Every user-level thread descriptor saves the size of the batch that they originally were targeted to. User-level threads in the shared queue are traversed and the saved batch size is checked for each thread. If the saved batch size is smaller than the current scheduler batch size then the scheduler batch is resized (figure 5.7).

The granularity of thread is identified by the batch size on which it should have been queued before being overflowed into the shared queue. For example if user-level threads were assigned to a scheduler with batch size 10 but the batch is full, these threads are queued into the shared queue. The batch size is saved into the thread descriptor as it is considered an indication of the threads granularity hence while retrieving user-level threads batch sizes could resize themselves.

YIELD

The programmer opt to set the swapping threshold *yield_tresh* which is saved in the scheduler descriptor. The swapping threshold is a threshold placed on the number of context switches that occur before the local scheduler batch is swapped with another batch from the shared queue. The idea behind the threshold is so that we ensure to service all user-level threads. This swapping ensure that no user-level thread will starve for computational time on the shared queue. Each scheduler has a yield counter which monitors the number of yields. Every time the *yield()* is called the yield counter is incremented. Before executing the normal yield routine, the yield counter is compared to the threshold. If the counter exceeds the threshold then the local batch is swapped. While retrieving a batch of user-level threads from the shared queue, the same variable batch

Figure 5.7: Variable Batch Sizing

size mechanism as dequeuing is employed. After retrieving a batch of user-level threads, the scheduler local batch is inserted in the shared queue. In the case that the context threshold has not been breached, the yielding mechanism will retrieve a user-level thread from the local queue and then queue up the yielded user-level thread in the local queue too. If the local queue is found empty the yielded user-level thread will return and continue execution.

RESULTS

In this chapter we shall give an account for the results obtained from various parts of the implementation especially the different queue strategies. We also discuss results obtained from the memory manager and spin-lock. The results were all timed on a Microsoft Windows XP version 5.1.2600. The architecture was a Dual Intel Xeon 2.4Ghz, 512KB level 2 cache, with 512MB of main memory. Visual Studio 2002 version 7.0.9466 was used as the programming IDE using .NET framework version 1.0.3705.

6.1 TIMER

Windows standard timers are fairly coarse-grained and are not reliable to time events less than a second hence it makes it difficult to time a snippet of code with nanosecond resolution making it further difficult to optimise the code. A better solution is to use the Win32 *QueryPerformanceCount()* function which is a high resolution timer. Such timers make use of a counter built inside an Intel-based chip since the pentium II. On startup the Intel-based chip uses a 64 bit register to keep track of the elapsed clock-ticks. The use of a 64 bit register is imperative because a 32 bit register can only count up to 2 billion clock-ticks [3]. Modern processors can perform 2 billion clock ticks in just around one second and hence a 32 bit register would be useless after powering up the machine for just a few seconds. The register in which the 64 bit counter is contained is a machine-specific-register (MSR). On executing the *RDTSC* instruction, the high order 32 bits are loaded into the EDX register and the lower order loaded into EAX register. The processor increments the time stamp counter MSR every clock cycle and resets it to 0 when the processor is reset [9]. Intel guarantees, architecturally, that the time stamp counter frequency and configuration will be such that it will not wraparound within 10 years after being reset to 0. The period for counter wrap is several thousands of years in the Intel Xeon [10].

Our nanosecond resolution timer which is used throughout the benchmarks, makes use of a processor instruction *RDTSC* discussed above. The timer starts by calling the *start_ticker()* function which executes the *RDTSC* instruction. The instruction loads the 64 bit time stamp register into EDX and EAX registers. The latter registers are read and saved in a local variable for future use (algorithm 6.1). The timer is terminated on a call to *end_ticker()* which re-executes the *RDTSC*

Algorithm 6.1 Start Ticker

```

_asm
{
    RDTSC
    mov end_ticks.int32val.i32[0], eax
    mov end_ticks.int32val.i32[4], edx
}

```

instruction and save the contents of EDX and EAX register. By subtracting the start time stamp from the end timer time stamp, we would have the number of clock-ticks that took place between *start_ticker()* and *end_ticker()*. The clock-ticks could then be converted to milliseconds by dividing the ticks by the processor frequency (Hz). The total timer overhead is about 100 ticks which is not subtracted from the benchmarks.

6.2 MEMORY MANAGER

The following benchmarks compare the time taken to create 5000 threads each using a stack of 64KB using *malloc()* and *user_malloc()*.

	Ticks	Total Time (μ s)	Individual Time (μ s)
<i>user_malloc()</i>	8403116	3507	0.7
<i>malloc()</i>	2711798948	1131680	226

Table 6.1: Memory Allocation Benchmark

The results clearly show the extra overhead when using *malloc()*. The immense overhead incurred by using *malloc* raised suspicion on why is *malloc* so slow. To find out more about Windows *malloc()* we ran some tests on *malloc()* by allocating different byte sizes and monitoring the time taken to allocate each different size.

Figure 6.1: `malloc()` Benchmark

Figure 6.1 shows the time taken to allocate different sizes of bytes. The graph shows that the time taken grows linearly while allocating the first 500000 bytes then while allocating more than 500000 bytes the time taken drops drastically. The result could be explained that windows try to fill in small empty pockets of memory when allocating relatively small amounts of memory. 500000 bytes seems to be a variable threshold where Windows just decides to allocate memory without filling up empty pockets and hence performs less memory management routines which is an indication to the drastically reduced overhead when allocating a size of greater than 500000 bytes.

6.3 SPIN-LOCK

In this section we shall benchmark the spin-lock synchronisation construct and the Windows critical section construct. Two tests were performed, the first is a routine of 20,000 lock entries and leaves and the second is the same routine but with contention. The spin-lock used for the benchmarks is a spin-lock which spins on a read and not a write.

	Ticks	Total Time (μs)	Individual Time (μs)
Spin-Lock	5239096	2186	0.11
Critical Section	6828844	2849	0.14

Table 6.2: Spin-Lock vs Windows Critical Section

Table 6.2 shows the results of from both our spin-lock and Windows critical section. The benchmark measured the time taken for 20,000 consecutive lock entry and release. The results show that user-level spin-lock is slightly faster than Windows critical section. Windows critical sections only access the kernel when the lock is found locked. In our first benchmark, the lock is never found occupied hence Windows critical sections will not access the kernel which is the reason why the critical section results in similar performance to the spin-lock.

	Ticks	Total Time (μs)	Individual Time (μs)
Spin-Lock	49883630	20817	1.04
Critical Section	638242356	266349	13.317

Table 6.3: Spin-Lock vs Windows Critical Section With Contention

Table 6.3 shows the results obtained from the same benchmark (i.e. 20,000 lock entry and leave) but with the difference that contention was induced in the test by executing a thread in parallel which continually accesses and frees the locked section. As expected the critically section performed much slower than the the spin-lock because the windows critical section suspends the thread when the lock is not available. Suspension access the kernel and hence incurs the extra overhead.

6.4 SHARED RUN-QUEUE

In this section we discuss the results obtained from the implementation of a shared run-queue strategy. Implementation details discussed in section 5.2.1.

6.4.1 QUEUING

The queuing benchmark is the time taken to queue 5000 user-level threads using a shared run-queue strategy. The user-level threads are only queued using

Run-Queue	Ticks	Total Time (μs)	Individual Time (μs)
shared	2941792	1228	0.25

Table 6.4: Shared Run-Queue Benchmark: Queuing

one scheduler and hence one processor. Since only one scheduler is queuing the user-level threads there is no queue lock contention which arises when two or more schedulers are racing to acquire the queue lock. The symmetric multiprocessor queuing routine still has more instructions than the same routine used for a uni-processor scheduler. In a uni-processor scheduler, queue locks are non-existent and hence the extra instructions to acquire a lock are avoided. Our SMP queue routine is also responsible for waking up any idling schedulers which would also be non-existent in a uni-processor scheduler because there would not be any schedulers to wake up. In SMP every time the scheduler is entered, the identity has to be established as discussed in section 5.1.2 which also incurs an extra overhead.

6.4.2 CONTEXT SWITCHING

In context switching we measure the average time taken to switch between user-level threads. Context switching is the main mechanism behind scheduling hence it is imperative to measure such an event because an overhead in context switching will incur a greater overhead in the whole system. In this benchmark we measure the time taken to execute 200 user-level threads where each will yield, i.e. perform a context switch, 10,000 times hence performing 2,000,000 context switches in all. The benchmark also includes the time taken to queue the user-level threads because with multiple schedulers, a queued user-level thread can start executing immediately by a different scheduler.

	Ticks	Total Time (μs)	Individual Time (μs)
one_processor	2617332016	1092257	0.55
two_processor	4297973676	1793617	0.90

Table 6.5: Shared Run-Queue Benchmark: Context Switching

At first glance the results are staggering. The `one_processor` proved to be almost twice as fast as its `two_processor` counterpart, something which one would expect to be the other way round. The `one_processor` is in fact 63% faster than the

two_processor benchmark. The main reason behind such a surprise is due to queue contention. The 200 user-level threads used for the benchmark are considered to be fine-grained threads because they had no work to do just yielding for 10,000 times which is not considered to be useful work. This fine granularity causes multiple schedulers to continuously context switch and hence continuously try to access the shared queue. This queue contention forces a scheduler to spin on a lock while waiting to acquire the shared queue resource. This problem is non-existent in the one_processor benchmark because the lock would never be locked so when the scheduler tries to enter the lock, it succeeds first time around. In the two_processor, every context switch is wasting on average $0.35\mu s$ spinning on a spin-lock which protects the shared queue. Another important locked shared resource is the memory manager but does not pose as much contention as the shared run-queue.

6.4.3 GRANULARITY

As we have seen in section 6.4.2 a single scheduler¹ is much faster than two schedulers using a shared queue strategy. We also pointed out that the fine-granularity of such threads incurred contention at the shared queue hence degrading the whole system throughput. In the granularity test we hope that by increasing the granularity of such threads, we decrease the queue contention and hence observe a better performance from the two_processor. The granularity benchmark is accomplished by executing 200 user-level threads each yielding 10,000 times but with the difference that each user-level thread has to accomplish some work before yielding. The work is imposed onto the user-level thread by using a loop. Each user-level thread has to loop for a number of times, depending on the granularity, before calling the *yield()* function.

In the snippet of code shown in algorithm 6.3, g is the granularity given to the user-level thread. g is varied from 0 to 1000 to produce user-level threads with different granularity. Every time the benchmark is executed, it performs 2,000,000 context switches over 200 user-level threads. Figure 6.2 depicts the effect of varying the user-level thread granularity for a single processor scheduler and as well as a dual symmetric processor scheduler. The result shows that at higher user-level granularity, the dual scheduler runs much faster than a single processor scheduler. In fact as we see later on at granularity 1000, the dual

¹hereinafter processor and scheduler are used interchangeably

Algorithm 6.2 Shared Run-Queue: Context Switch Benchmark

```
UThread *worker[200];
BigInt s_tick;
int i;
for(i = 0;i < 200;i++)
{
    worker[i] = UThreadCreate(foo,DEFAULT_SS,0);
}
s_tick = start_ticker();

for(i = 0;i < 200;i++)
{
    enqueue(worker[i]);
}
for(i = 0;i < 200;i++)
{
    join(worker[i]);
}

end_ticker(s_tick);

void foo()
{
    int count = 0;
    while(count < 10000)
    {
        yield();
        count++;
    }
}
```

Algorithm 6.3 Shared Run-Queue: Granularity Benchmark

```
void foo() {
    int i;
    int count = 0;
    int n = 0;
    while(count < 10000)
    {
        for(i = 0; i < (g * 10);i++)
            n+=1;

        yield();
        count++;
    }
}
```

processor is almost running twice as fast as the single processor which is what we want to achieve. This achievement occurs as a result of reducing shared queue contention because we increased the workload done by each user-level thread hence the schedulers will spend more time executing user-level thread instructions than spinning on locks to acquire shared resources.

In figure 6.3 we zoom in on the initial part of the graph shown in figure 6.2. The graph shows that due to contention for shared resources, finer-grained user-level threads are not scheduled efficiently on multiple processors, in fact a single scheduler can do the job much faster. The graph also indicates that around granularity of 14g both schedulers ran at the same speed. From then on the contention started to reduce on the shared queue and the SMP scheduler started executing user-level threads much faster than its single processor counterpart. Something which is very much interesting is the fact that at granularity 0g the SMP scheduler is much slower than at granularity 5g. This is an indication of how much contention exists with the finest-grained user-level threads. As soon as the granularity has been increased slightly, the contention immediately drops and executing coarser-grained user-level threads became faster. In fact the time taken to execute 200 fine-grained threads (0g) took about the same time to execute 200 user-level threads with a granularity of about 30g. The speedup achieved by using a shared run-queue strategy is shown in figure 6.4 which clearly shows that

Figure 6.2: Shared Run-Queue Benchmark: Granularity

Figure 6.3: Shared Run-Queue Benchmark: Granularity

the system suffers while scheduling fine-grained user-level threads. The graph also clearly depicts that by increasing the granularity of the threads, a better work gain is achieved. In fact at around granularity 600 the system is working at a speedup of 1.91 which indicates that the dual processor system is working 1.91 times faster than uni-processor. The latter result is quite satisfactory when compared to the speedup achieved for 0 granularity threads (0.62) which indicates that the dual processor system is 38% slower than the uni-processor.

Figure 6.4: Shared Run-Queue Benchmark: Speedup

6.5 PER-PROCESSOR RUN-QUEUE

In this section we will discuss results obtained from the per-processor run-queue implementation. Implementation details are discussed in section 5.2.2.

6.5.1 QUEUING

In queuing we examine the time taken to queue 5000 user-level threads into one local scheduler queue. Only one scheduler is used in this experiment, the second scheduler is not run because it would cause a kernel call to suspend itself

as no user-level threads were assigned to it. The suspend call would effect the reading. The results in table 6.6 clearly show that the per-processor queuing

Run-Queue	Ticks	Total Time (μ s)	Individual Time (μ s)
shared	2941792	1228	0.25
per-processor	2024304	845	0.17

Table 6.6: Per-Processor Run-Queue Benchmark: Queuing

routine is 32% faster then a shared queue routine. This difference in speed has no connection with any contention which is the common overhead associated with shared resources but its more a matter of implementation. The shared queue strategy uses a circular linked list with two access pointers while each scheduler local queue in a per-processor queue strategy uses a linked list with just one access pointer pointing to the head. Also the shared queue strategy has the slight overhead of acquiring the queue lock which, in the benchmark, is guaranteed to be always free when the scheduler tries to enter because no other scheduler will be contending for the lock. The per-processor local queue routine only accesses one pointer which points to the head of the queue. Any new user-level threads are queued in front of the head as opposed being queued at the tail. A dummy node also removes the need to check if the queue is empty on every queue routine because it is always taken full granted that the queue contains at least one node. The local queue is not circular hence less pointers need to be set.

6.5.2 CONTEXT SWITCHING

The same context switching experiment used in the shared run-queue strategy benchmark was also carried out using the per-processor queue strategy (section 6.4.2). The per-processor strategy is aimed to address the common shared queue strategy faults which are, mainly, the excessive queue contention and the lack of processor cache usage due to the continuous migration of user-level threads between different processors.

The reduced overhead from queue contention is clearly evident in table 6.7. The per-processor dual processor is almost 4 times as fast as the shared dual processor strategy. Also a decrease in context switch time is evident when comparing the per-processor uni-processor with the uni-processor shared queue strategy context switching. This decrease in context switch time is mainly due a simpler context

Queue Strategy	Ticks	Total Time (μ s)	Individual Time (μ s)
shared one_processor	2617332016	1092257	0.55
shared two_processor	4297973676	1793617	0.90
per-processor one_processor	2122002060	885548	0.44
per-processor two_processor	1108217856	462478	0.23

Table 6.7: Per-Processor Run-Queue Benchmark: Context Switching

switch routine. Unlike the shared queue schedulers, the per-processors shows a clear increase in context switch speed over its uni-processor counterpart. The dual processor is almost twice (1.91) as fast the single processor which clearly indicates that by removing shared queue contention we can obtain better performance. The context switch algorithm 6.4 used to benchmark the per-processor strategy is slightly different than the shared queue algorithm 6.2. An extra parameter is passed to the *enqueue()* routine which identifies the scheduler id onto which the user-level thread should be queued hence it is the programmer's responsibility for assigning user-level threads to specific schedulers' local queues. In other words the programmer is responsible for balancing the load over all processors. In our benchmark we split the load evenly over the two processors by alternating user-level threads over the different schedulers. A pure per-processor queue scheduling strategy does not offer any mechanism for load balancing and it is the main drawback in such a strategy.

6.5.3 GRANULARITY

This granularity benchmark is aimed to investigate the scheduling times when scheduling user-level threads of different granularity whilst using the per-processor queue strategy. The benchmark algorithm is identical to that used in the shared run-queue strategy, algorithm 6.3. The graph in figure 6.5 clearly shows the dual per-processor scheduler out performs its counterpart, single per-processor scheduler in all granularity ranges. Although, at first glance the per-processor seems to perform somewhat like the shared run-queue strategy, the main difference are noticed at fine granularity.

The fine granularity timings for per-processor and shared run-queue strategies using dual processors are shown in figure 6.6. The graph clearly shows the differences between the per-processor and shared run-queue strategies while

Algorithm 6.4 Per-Processor Run-Queue: Context Switch Benchmark

```
UThread *worker[200];
BigInt s_tick;
int i;
for(i = 0;i < 200;i++)
{
    worker[i] = UThreadCreate(foo,DEFAULT_SS,0);
}
s_tick = start_ticker();

for(i = 0;i < 200;i++)
{
    enqueue(worker[i],i % 2 + 1);
}
for(i = 0;i < 200;i++)
{
    join(worker[i]);
}

end_ticker(s_tick);

void foo()
{
    int count = 0;
    while(count < 10000)
    {
        yield();
        count++;
    }
}
```

Figure 6.5: Per-Processor Run-Queue Benchmark: Granularity

Figure 6.6: Per-Processor and Shared Run-Queue Benchmark: Granularity

scheduling fine-grained user-level threads. The per-processor scheduler does not suffer from any queue contention because the strategy implements a local queue for each scheduler hence there are no locks to acquire access to a shared queue which removes the possibility of schedulers wasting time spinning on queue locks. At coarser-grained user-level threads both schedulers perform similar with the shared run queue performing slower. A per-processor strategy is more cache friendly because user-level threads never migrate between processors hence cache invalidations are decreased whereas in a shared queue strategy, user-level threads can continuously migrate between processors which will typically invalidate processor caches. The latter would definitely incur an extra overhead and could be one of the reasons why the shared queue strategy performed slower than the per-processor at coarser-grained user-level threads. The speedup shown in figure 6.7,

Figure 6.7: Per-Processor Run-Queue Benchmark: Speedup

clearly shows the difference in performance between the per-processor and shared run-queue strategies. Whilst the shared queue has a very poor performance at finer granularity, the per-processor performs near perfect. The latter shows the power of per-processor scheduling. This performance is credited to two areas, first the elimination of shared queue contention which is a killer in the shared queue strategy and the second is a more cache friendly scheduling, discussed previously.

The main drawback of per-processor scheduling strategy is that the load balance is taken care by the programmer, in our benchmark, we evenly distributed the load on both schedulers hence achieving perfect load balance. In reality load balancing is not as straight forward as our benchmark and hence the system could easily suffer processor starvation where a processor idles while other processors are overloaded with user-level threads. Starvation could easily degrade the whole system throughput to an extent that a per-processor strategy would perform even worse than a shared run-queue strategy.

A per-processor strategy immediately accelerates to an almost ideal speedup even at the finest grained user-level threads but the strategy could easily fall into the load imbalance trap. Some techniques exist which try to add a load balancing mechanism to the per-processor strategy. One such mechanism is referred to as *work-stealing* discussed in section 2.8. Basically, an idling scheduler will try to *steal* work from other schedulers' local queue. Although the idea works, the thread migration mechanism can incur too much overhead degrading the system throughput.

6.6 VARIABLE BATCH RUN-QUEUE

Variable batching, introduced by K. Vella [25], is aimed to overcome the per-processor shortcomings. It could be considered to be a hybrid of both a shared run-queue strategy and a per-processor strategy. The hybrid version aims to exploit both strategies' advantages while minimizing their respective drawbacks (section 5.2.3).

6.6.1 QUEUING

The queuing test is similar to the previous strategies. In the benchmark, 5000 user-level threads are queued using the batching queuing strategy. Only one scheduler was used to perform this benchmark. Two benchmarks were performed on this strategy, one with a batch size of 10, 4090 are forced to be queued on the shared queue, and another with a batch size of 5000 in which the shared queue is not accessed. The results in table 6.8 indicated that queuing time depends on the batch size. A batch size of 10, forced the scheduler to queue 4090 user-level threads into the shared queue hence incurring an overhead associated with shared queue in fact, with a batch size of 10 the variable batching is somewhat slower than a shared queue routine. Apart from having the overhead associated with

a shared queue, the enqueue routine is more complex hence more instructions need to be executed which lead to a further overhead. Using a batch size of 5000, matching the number of user-level threads queued, the queuing time is immediately reduced because all user-level threads are queued in the local queue and no user-level thread overflows into the shared queue.

Run-Queue	Ticks	Total Time (μ s)	Individual Time (μ s)
shared	2941792	1228	0.25
per-processor	2024304	845	0.17
variable batch 10	3176776	1326	0.27
variable batch 5000	2410140	1006	0.20

Table 6.8: Batch Run-Queue Benchmark: Queuing

6.6.2 CONTEXT SWITCHING

The context switching benchmark is taken by executing 200 user-level threads whilst each yields 10,000 times. This benchmark is the same used with the previous queue strategies. For the purpose of this experiment batch sizes were both set to 10 with a swapping threshold of 100 i.e. after every 100 context switches performed by a scheduler, the local batch is swapped with another batch of user-level threads from the shared queue. A separate benchmark was also taken with a threshold of 10,000 whilst another was taken with no swapping. 10 user-level threads are assigned to each scheduler and the remaining 180 are queued in the shared queue.

Context switch benchmarks indicate that batching is also a powerful strategy because it is capable of achieving results close to the per-processor strategy. The context switch overhead depends a lot on the size of the batch used and the threshold set on the swapping mechanism. Increasing the swapping threshold resulted in a slight context switch time decrease due to a reduction in shared queue access. Increasing the batch sizes while disabling swapping also decreased context switch time.

6.6.3 GRANULARITY

The first part of the granularity test uses static batching rather than variable. Static batching refers to the fact that all schedulers are assigned the same batch

size and the batch size does not change during execution. In the first set of benchmarks we investigate the combination of swapping threshold and batch size. For each test case, 200 user-level threads are executed each yielding 10,000 times and varying granularity g . The results in figure 6.8 show the time taken to execute user-level threads with different granularity. Each scheduler was assigned a batch size of 10 and a swapping threshold of 100. The results clearly show that the dual processor scheduler performed much better than the single processor scheduler. Changing the batch sizes and swapping threshold can have a noticeable impact on the performance of schedulers.

Figure 6.9 shows the effect of setting the batch size to 100 while retaining the swap threshold to also 100. The performance with a batch size of 100 decreased. The reason for the degradation is due to the swapping mechanism. A swapping threshold of 100 means that each scheduler swaps its local queue every 100 context switches, since we have 2 million context switches in the whole benchmark then 20,000 swaps occur which results in 10,000 swaps for each scheduler. On every swap the scheduler has to iterate through the shared queue to find the last user-level thread which shall makeup part of the local batch (this iteration is imperative because each user-level thread has to be tested for a granularity criteria which would would variably adjust the schedulers batch size discussed in section 5.2.3) and also iterate through its local queue to find the tail node (because only one pointer is held which points to the head of the queue). With a batch size of 100, every swap has to iterate a maximum of 200 nodes, 100 in the local queue and 100 to retrieve the new batch. This iteration incurs an extra overhead especially

Queue Strategy	Ticks	Total Time (μs)	Individual Time (μs)
shared two_processor	4297973676	1793617	0.90
per-processor two_processor	1108217856	462478	0.23
variable batch one_processor	2285682140	953854	0.48
batch two_processor with 100 swap threshold	1221480288	509744	0.2549
batch two_processor with 10,000 swap threshold	1188991580	496186	0.2481
batch two_processor with no swap batch size 100	1147907068	479041	0.24

Table 6.9: Batch Run-Queue Benchmark: Context Switching

when repeated 10,000 times. While performing the swap iterations, the shared queue is locked and hence any other scheduler need to spin while waiting to the shared queue lock, this spinning further increases the overhead due to the increase in granularity of the critical section.

The effect of the queue contention contention can be clearly shown in the speedup graph 6.10 which shows that with a batch size of 100 and a swap-threshold of 100, shared queue contention decreases the speedup while scheduling fine grained user-level threads. One must note that having a huge batch size and a relatively small swapping threshold does not make much sense because the batch will rarely (in our case never) dequeue more than a few user-level threads before swapping the batch.

Figure 6.8: Batch Run-Queue Benchmark: Granularity

The speedup achieved by all strategies could be observed in figure 6.10. the graph clearly shows the difference in speedup between the shared queue strategy and the per-processor, batch queue strategies especially while scheduling fine grained user-level threads. Two variants of the batch strategy where tested one

Figure 6.9: Batch Run-Queue Benchmark: Different Batch Sizes

Figure 6.10: Batch Run-Queue Benchmark: Speedup

with a batch size of 10^2 and another with batch size of 100^3 . The almost perfect speedup obtained by the per-processor and batch-10 is a result of the yielding mechanism. Since the scheduler's local queue is only accessed by one pointer which points to head, queue manipulation occurs around the only one pointer. The latter produces a depth-first execution style as opposed to a two pointer list which produces a breadth-first execution style. The yielding routine will first dequeue the first user-level thread pointed by the head pointer and then queue the old thread which will become the head, on the next yield the threads swap place again. This execution style is very cache friendly because, generally, the next user-level thread to run is already cached as it would have also been than last thread to run.

Using a queue with two pointer(head and tail) the queued user-level thread will be queued on the tail and has to wait its turn to execute hence there would be a great chance that any cached data associated with such a thread would be flushed out and data has to be reloaded into cache when the user-level thread turn is next. The queue with only one pointer also has its drawbacks mainly noticed while swapping as the local queue has to be traversed so as to find the tail node which is needed to insert the local queue into the shared queue. This produces an overhead which grows linearly with the size of the batch, $O(N)$. The swapping overhead can be noticed in the batch-100 speedup where the overhead drastically reduced the initial speedup.

Up till now we have not discussed anything about variable batching, what we did so far is pretty much static batching because schedulers all had the same batch size. Variable batching addresses a common problem that could arise with static batching, the problem is mostly evident when scheduling a mixture of fine-grained and coarse-grained user-level threads. If, while scheduling coarse-grain user-level threads, the batch size is set relatively big, then schedulers might idle while another scheduler still has coarse-grain user-level threads on its local queue. The latter will cause a load imbalance. Variable batching allows the programmer to set different batch size for each scheduler. This feature allows the programmer to group user-level threads with different granularity and batch them up on different schedulers with different batch sizes as an effort to reduce the load imbalance. Typically the programmer would group coarse-grain user-level threads and schedule them on a scheduler with a relative small batch size this

²hereinafter referred to as batch-10

³hereinafter referred to as batch-100

would avoid queuing too much coarse-grain user-level threads on the local queue, preventing any other scheduler from executing them. The programmer would also group fine-grain threads and schedule them on a scheduler with a relatively big batch size because such threads are expected to execute in no time and hence could better exploit cache potential.

Batch Sizes	Ticks	Total Time (s)
100 , 100	44990225484	18.8
75 , 75	34077963852	14.2
100 , 5	23381487732	9.8
75 , 5	24242581312	10.1

Table 6.10: Variable Batch Run-Queue Benchmark: Different Batch Sizes

Table 6.10 shows the time taken to execute a mixture of fine-grained user-level threads and coarse-grained user-level threads. In the experiment 200 user-level threads were executed each yielding 10,000 times, 100 threads of the 200 were assigned a granularity of 0g and the remaining 100g were assigned a granularity of 1000. Swapping threshold was disabled for this experiment so as to force swapping only when the batch queue is empty. The latter would aid to further analyze the results. The fine-grain and coarse-grain user-level threads were grouped and queued on separate schedulers (in the case of the 100 and 5 ratio, fine-grained threads were queued into the scheduler with a batch size of 100 and with the 75,5 ratio fine-grain threads were queued in the scheduler with the batch size of 75).

The first batch size in table 6.10 is set to 100 for both schedulers. This size forces the schedulers to act in a per-processor strategy and hence the shared queue is not used. The result shows the effect of load imbalance that occurs. This situation arises as the scheduler with the fine-grain threads finishes executing its batch and sits idling because the shared queue is empty. The second scheduler queued with coarse-grain threads is overloaded with work but there is no way to share the load with the idling processor. The second scenario is a batch size of 75 for both schedulers hence 50 user-level threads are queued in the shared queue half of which are fine-grain and the rest are coarse-grain. The result is much more efficient than the first because the first scheduler executes its 75 fine-grained user-level threads and instead of idling will obtain the remaining 50 in the shared queue so that it executes the remaining 25 fine-grain threads along with

the 25 coarse-grain threads. Although this scenario is faster, a load imbalance is still evident as the first scheduler will execute the 25 coarse-grain threads then idles while there are still user-level threads on the second scheduler's local queue.

The third scenario uses variable batching where the schedulers are assigned different batch sizes. The coarse-grain scheduler is assigned a batch size of 5 (which is relatively small) this batch size only holds 5 user-level threads on its local queue and the remaining 95 are queued on the shared queue so that other schedulers can execute them instead of idling. The scheduler targeted for fine-grain threads is assigned a batch size of 100 so that it does not waste computational time obtaining user-level threads from the shared queue and better exploits the cache. Once the scheduler with a batch of 100 finishes executing its local queue, it starts queuing another batch from the shared queue but if obtains the whole 95 coarse-grain threads, the second scheduler will not find any threads on the shared queue and idles which will cause a load imbalance. Due to this reason the scheduler with a batch of 100 will start queuing user-level threads from the shared queue and resizes its batch to 5 so as to queue only 5 user-level threads. In the 4th case, the first scheduler has a batch size of 75, after executing all its user-level threads, the scheduler tries to obtain another 75 threads from the shared queue. Since only the first 25 in the queue are fine-grain threads, the batch size is resized after queuing 25 user-level threads to 5 hence only queuing a further 5 which totals to a batch size of 30 ($25 + 5$). Although this mechanism improves the load balancing, it also incurs an extra overhead due to the more complex swapping operations.

CONCLUSION

We conclude our thesis by given an account of what has been accomplished in our project while also indicating any system drawbacks. We shall then discuss any future work that can be accomplished.

7.1 ACCOMPLISHMENTS

In our thesis we were able to create and schedule user-level threads on a Windows XP platform. A user-level memory manager was implemented as an effort to reduce kernel activity during user-level thread scheduling. The scheduler was also implemented to schedule user-level threads on a symmetric multiprocess Windows XP multitasking platform. To our knowledge no other user-level thread scheduler for symmetric multiprocessors has been implemented on a Windows NT platform. The latter fact turned out to be an obstacle because relatively no information could be found on how Windows manages low level routines which could have been of a great help towards our implementation.

In our thesis we also implemented and investigated three different queue strategies. Such strategies are *shared run-queue*, *per-processor run-queue* and *variable batch run-queue*. The results from the different queue strategies where compared against each other and the outcome was discussed. Other common scheduler areas were also timed which include the memory manager and the locking mechanisms.

7.2 DRAWBACKS

Our thesis is targeted to offer an insight into Windows platform user-level thread scheduling and is not aimed to be a commercial project. Due to lack of time not enough testing was performed to prove the scheduler bug free, one must note that a testing session could take between 5 minutes and hours because parallel programming generates bugs without any pattern of frequencies and hence a bug could show up after hours on end of testing or just after a few seconds.

The common scheduler i.e. the part of the scheduler common to all queuing strategies, is not optimized to its fullest. The main areas that could immediately reduce the overhead are the scheduler identifying system which uses windows extension, *thread-local storage (TLS)*, and scheduler function calling. A common practice in user-level thread scheduler implementation is to hash-define most functions to remove the overhead of function calling. Due to lack of time and due to our thesis being a prototype, we did not hash-define most functions. The latter would facilitate code understanding in the case that future researches shall continue work on the scheduler.

Apart of the immediate optimizations, we believe that further optimizations will definitely contribute to reducing the scheduling overhead as there is a much more room for optimisations. User-level semaphores in the per-processor and batch queue strategy were not implemented due to lack of time. User-level semaphores were only implemented in shared-queue strategy.

7.3 FUTURE WORK

The work that could still be accomplished on the scheduler is unlimited. One of the main features that could be added to the scheduler is block handling where a user-level thread could block for I/O and hence block the whole scheduler hence preventing further user-level threads from executing on a specific processor. One such way to solve this problem is to use kernel activations.

Another enhancement could be the implementation of inter-thread communication system which would bypass the kernel while accessing the hardware network cards. This would enable the scheduler to schedule user-level threads on parallel distributed systems hence executing user-level threads locally as well as remotely on other single or multiprocessor machines.

Priority scheduling could also be introduced in the system which would enable user-level threads with different priorities to be queued in different run-queues hence processor resources could be directed towards tasks with high priority before executing lower priority threads.

With a fully functional user-level thread scheduler, the next step would be to fully hide the runtime scheduler from the programmer. This could be achieved

by a pre-processor which could pre-process user-programmed code and convert it to C intermediate code which would have all the necessary scheduler library calls inserted automatically such as Cilk [21].

7.4 CLOSING NOTE

User-level thread scheduling on symmetric multiprocessors has already been successfully achieved on non-Windows platforms, our project aimed to reveal low level Windows internals while implementing the user-level thread scheduler. The lack of such information is an indication why computer scientists frequently resort to other platforms to carry out their research.

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